

Solutions & technologies available within and across regions
D2.2

Authors: Daniele Antichi, Christian Frasconi, Lorenzo Gagliardi, Massimo Sbrana, Lorenzo Gabriele Tramacere, Nicoleta Darra, Olga Kriezi, Borja Espejo Garcia, Kevin Godfrey, Camille Guilbert, Fanny Prezman, Thomas Börjesson, Javier Francisco Rigueiro Rodriguez, Rosa Maria Mosquera Losada, Maksims Filipovics, Viktorija Zagorska

Edited by: Nicoleta Darra & Olga Kriezi (AUA)

Table of content

Document Information	3
Document history	4
Abbreviations	5
Participants	6
Document summary	7
<i>Executive Summary</i>	7
Document content	8
<i>Part. 1 Introduction</i>	8
<i>Part. 2 Methodology</i>	10
2.1 Methodology for systematic scientific literature review.....	10
2.2 Methodology for patents search.....	14
2.3 Methodology for European and national research projects review	14
<i>Part. 3 Description of the outcomes</i>	17
3.1 Outcomes of the systematic scientific literature review	17
3.2 Outcomes of the patents search.....	21
3.3 Outcomes of the European projects search.....	22
3.4 Outcomes of the National projects search	26
<i>Part. 4 Conclusions</i>	29
4.1 Summary conclusions on scientific literature review	29
4.2 Summary conclusions on patent search	29
4.3 Summary conclusions on European and National projects search.....	30
<i>Part. 5 General Conclusions and Final Remarks</i>	31
Appendix 1. Search strings used for the scientific literature review	33

Document Information

Project Acronym	OPER8
Project Title	European Thematic Network for unlocking the full potential of Operational Groups on alternative weed control
EU Project Officer	Celine Choquer
Project Coordinator	Spyros Fountas
Project Duration	October 2022 - September 2025 (36 months)
Deliverable No	2.2
Dissemination Level	PU ¹
Work Package	WP2: Capturing grassroots needs and identifying solutions
Task	T2.2
Lead Beneficiary	UNIFI
Lead Author	Daniele Antichi (UNIFI)
Co - Authors	Christian Frascioni (UNIFI), Lorenzo Gagliardi (UNIFI), Massimo Sbrana (UNIFI), Lorenzo Gabriele Tramacere (UNIFI), Nicoleta Darra (AUA), Olga Kriezi (AUA), Borja Espejo Garcia (AUA), Kevin Godfrey (ADAS), Camille Guilbert (IFV), Fanny Prezman (IFV), Thomas Börjesson (AGROVAST), Javier Francisco Rigueiro Rodriguez (USC), Rosa Maria Mosquera Losada (USC), Maksims Filipovics (LLU), Viktorija Zagorska (LLU)
Peer - Reviewed	Camille Guilbert (IFV), Francisco Javier Rodriguez Rigueiro (USC)
Due Date of Deliverable	31 August 2023
Actual Submission Date	05 September 2023

TABLE 1: DOCUMENT INFORMATION

¹ PU = public | PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services) | RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services) | CO= Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
1	31/08/2023	1 st Draft Deliverable 2.2	N/A	Daniele Antichi
2	04/09/2023	Reviewed version of the Deliverable 2.2	Language edit, graphical representations of data	Nicoleta Darra, Olga Kriezi, Camille Guilbert, Francisco Javier Rodriguez Rigueiro
3	05/09/2023	Final version of the Deliverable 2.2		Daniele Antichi

TABLE 2: DOCUMENT HISTORY

Abbreviations

EU	EUROPEAN UNION	OG	OPERATIONAL GROUP
WP	WORK PACKAGE	T	TASK
NNO	NATIONAL NETWORK OPERATOR	NN	NATIONAL NETWORK
NAP	NATIONAL ACTION PLAN	DOI	DIGITAL OBJECT IDENTIFIER
IPM	INTEGRATED PEST MANAGEMENT	CAP	COMMON AGRICULTURAL POLICY
IWM	INTEGRATED WEED MANAGEMENT	EPO	EUROPEAN PATENT OFFICE
AKIS	AGRICULTURAL KNOWLEDGE AND INNOVATION SYSTEMS	RDP	RURAL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM
EIP-AGRI	EUROPEAN INNOVATION PARTNERSHIP FOR AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTIVITY AND SUSTAINABILITY	CORDIS	COMMUNITY RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT INFORMATION SERVICE
DSS	DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEM	NUTS	NOMENCLATURE OF TERRITORIAL UNITS FOR STATISTICS

TABLE 3: ABBREVIATIONS

Participants

Participants		Contact
Agricultural University of Athens (AUA) Greece		Prof. Spyros Fountas sfountas@aual.gr
University of Santiago de Compostela (USC) Spain		Rosa Maria Losada Mosquera mrosa.mosquera.losada@usc.es
University of Pisa (UNIPI) Italy		Daniele Antichi daniele.antichi@unipi.it
Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies (LLU) Latvia		Jānis Jaško janis.jasko@llu.lv
RSK ADAS LTD (ADAS) UK		Lynn Tatnell Lynn.Tatnell@adas.co.uk
AGROVÅST Livsmedel AB (AGROVAST) Sweden		Thomas Börjesson thomas.borjesson@agrovast.se
Institut Français de la Vigne et du Vin (IFV) France		Eirios Hugo, Camille Guilbert eirios.hugo@vignevin.com camille.guilbert@vignevin.com
Farmers Parliament (ZSA) Latvia		Inga Berzina inga@zemniekusaeima.lv
Organic Research Centre (ORC) UK		Matt Smee Matt.s@organicresearchcentre.com
AGROMET P.C. (AGROMET) Greece		Aris Zamidis azamidis@tractorgps.gr

TABLE 4: PARTICIPANTS

Document summary

A state of the art of the scientific and practical knowledge available in the twenty-seven (27) countries of the European Union (EU-27) and the United Kingdom (UK) for weed control tactics alternative to herbicide use has been produced. The state of the art encompasses the latest scientific papers, findings from European and national projects, and patents developed within the past decade. The gathered information will undergo a systematic organization process and will be made publicly available to the Oper8 Network of Stakeholders. The accessibility will occur through the Oper8 inventory (T.2.3) embedded in Oper8 web platform, while also providing feedback for the development of National Action Plans (T2.4).

Executive Summary

This deliverable is the final outcome of Task 2.2 - Solutions & technologies available within and across regions. The deliverable comprises the present report and a dataset, included as annex in the form of an electronic worksheet. The document is organized into several discrete sections, each designed with a particular aim in mind, working collectively to provide an in-depth grasp of the subject matter. Part 1 serves as a starting point, providing an overview of the document's purpose and what readers can expect to find. It sets the stage for the subsequent parts by introducing the context and importance of alternative weed control.

Part 2 is dedicated to explaining the various methods and approaches employed throughout the document. This includes a detailed description of how the scientific literature review was conducted, the collection and analysis of European Research Projects documents, the compilation of National Research Projects documents, and the examination of patents registered in Europe. It is the foundation upon which the entire document is built.

Part 3 dives into the outcomes of the research efforts. In this Part, you will find the results, insights, and data gathered from the scientific literature review, European Research Projects, National Research Projects, and patent analysis. This section provides a factual and evidence-based account of the current state of knowledge and technological advancements in the field of Integrated Weed Management (IWM).

Part 4 serves as the endpoint of the document, where all the information and findings are synthesized into key takeaways and conclusions. It is a crucial section that distils the complexities of the research into actionable insights and findings that can guide decision-making and future directions in the realm of IWM.

Part 5 represents the concluding thoughts and reflections on the entire document. It offers a space for the authors and stakeholders to provide additional insights, discuss the broader implications of the research, and suggest potential avenues for further exploration or action. The dataset includes the outcomes of:

- a systematic scientific literature review
- the compilation of European Research Projects documents
- the compilation of National Research Projects documents
- a review of patents registered in Europe.

In essence, this dataset will provide a comprehensive overview of the scientific and practical knowledge on methods of weed control alternative to herbicide use. This will represent the starting point for discussion within national networks (WP1), preparation of national action plans (T2.4) and definition of best practices (WP3).

Document content

Part. 1 Introduction

One of the primary goals of Oper8 project is to develop National Action Plans for the widespread and promotion of weed control methods alternative to the use of herbicides. These methods are identified among a plethora of IWM methods with different potentials and constrains in terms of:

- i) Applicability: the extent to which these methods can be effectively used in major cropping systems, including arable crops, vineyards, olive trees, orchards, field vegetables and grasslands;
- ii) Readiness: the degree of readiness for the practical implementation of these methods;
- iii) Adaptability: the ability of these methods to conform to specific pedoclimatic conditions and socio-economic contexts.

The foundation for this systematic analysis was laid in T2.2 by identifying, collecting and reviewing all the available alternative weed control methods. The solution types/ sources considered have been: (i) solutions tested from the eight (8) Oper8 partner OGs; (ii) scientific (search on Scopus) and technical solutions available from EU-funded (via the EU Cordis platform) and national projects (via European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability – EIP-AGRI portal), as well as from EIP-AGRI focus groups' publications; and (iii) commercially available solutions. The systematic review was deliberately confined to knowledge generated within the geographical area of the EU-27 plus the UK over the past decade (01/01/2013-31/12/2022). These temporal and geographical constraints ensure that the Oper8 National Networks (NNs) stakeholders are equipped with the most advanced and regionally customised solutions.

The state of the art, that will be systematized and organised in the Oper8 inventory in T2.3, contains fundamental information. It allows the determination of i) which IWM tactics have been intensively explored by science, ii) which ones have related new patented technologies available, iii) specific conditions and for which of the most common European crops (arable crops, vineyards, olive trees, orchards, field vegetables and grasslands) alternative solutions to herbicide have been tested. Furthermore, it will serve as a valuable tool for pinpointing knowledge gaps and the absence of market-ready solutions for certain tactics. This may include innovative approaches like biocontrol products applicable to weed control or areas where alternatives to herbicide use are perceived overly complex or challenging for farmers to implement or are considered too expensive.

The state of the art serves as a starting point for discussions among Oper8 stakeholders within NNs. These discussions will revolve around the applicability of IWM methods in their respective countries, i.e., understanding the context in which solutions are already applied depending on the country, farm type and farmer profile, and technology uptake. At the same time, this compilation of solutions helps to avoid duplication with ongoing or completed projects and networks at the national or the European level. Therefore, the major aim followed in developing the state of the art is to simplify the process for end-users, making it easy to identify significant information sources, link these sources to specific IWM methods and access more detailed technical/operational information, when needed. This user-friendly approach will be reflected in the Oper8 inventory being developed in T2.3.

Finally, to categorise and structure the retrieved IWM solutions, the systematic review will rely on the framework of IWM developed by the EU-H2020 IWM PRAISE project (<https://iwmpraise.eu/>). This framework classifies IWM methods into five (5) pillars (01. Direct Control, 02. Field and soil management, 03. Cultivar choice and crop establishment, 04. Diverse cropping systems, 05. Monitoring and evaluation), each encompassing multiple tactics that align with three (3) primary strategies of weed control, i.e. reducing weed impact on crops, preventing weed establishment and reducing weed seed return (Figure 1) (Riemens et al., 2022). A detailed explanation of each tactic is available at <https://iwmpraise.eu/publications/- tool>.

FIGURE 1. THE FRAMEWORK OF INTEGRATED WEED MANAGEMENT DEVELOPED BY THE IWM PRAISE PROJECT (FROM RIEMENS ET AL., 2022). BLUE HEXAGONS CORRESPOND TO THE FIVE (5) IWM PILLARS, AND THE ORANGE, GREEN, AND GREY COLORS CHARACTERIZE THE TACTICS ACCORDING TO THE THREE (3) PRIMARY STRATEGIES OF WEED CONTROL.

It is important to note that the tactics centered on herbicide use (i.e., pre-emergence herbicide, post-emergence herbicide, patch/band spraying) were deliberately excluded from the Oper8 review, focusing on alternative to herbicide use solutions. Instead, the focus was solely placed on pre-harvest weed control which includes not only herbicides but also non-chemical alternatives, i.e., flaming, and other non-chemical products. Overall, this systematic review explored a total of thirty (30) IWM tactics.

The findings have been compiled in a dataset, supplemented as Annex 1 to this report. This dataset is structured as an MS-Excel folder, including individual worksheet for each section of the state of the art (i.e., scientific literature review, EU project outcomes, national research projects gathered in the EIP-AGRI website, patents registered at the European Patent Office).

This report outlines the methodology followed to produce each section and offers an overview of the major outcomes of the dataset.

Part. 2 Methodology

2.1 Methodology for systematic scientific literature review

The review of the scientific literature pertaining to IWM, alternative to herbicide methods was conducted as a systematic review, following the established protocol outlined by PRISMA (<http://www.prisma-statement.org/>). PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) is the international standard for systematic reviews and meta-analysis in scientific publications. We opted for a systematic review rather than a scope review due to the massive literature available on the topic of IWM that impeded a scope review, due to time constraints within the project. Moreover, the systematic approach was deemed suitable for replication in the evaluation of patents and other information sources. Among the different available scientific datasets, Scopus was chosen due to its comprehensive coverage of relevant scientific journals and topics associated with IWM.

The systematic review was structured through the following steps:

1. For all the tactics, a general scientific question was defined. The scientific question was “What is known about the effects of **NAME OF THE TACTIC** on weed control”?
2. For each tactic, the general scientific question was modified to incorporate the name of the tactic. Each component of the question, i.e., the knowledge source (“what is known”), the tactic itself (e.g., diverse cropping systems) and the response variable (“weed control”) was treated as an individual “topic”. These topics were further subdivided into sub-categories, reflecting various operations/elements associated with the tactic. For instance, consider the example of the tactic “Tillage type” (Figure 2):

What is known about the effects of tillage type on weed control?

Tillage	Type	Weed control
Conventional	Inversion	Yield
Reduced	Non-inversion	Biomass (Crop)
Conservative	Depth	Weed Biomass
Minimum	Timing	Weed density
No-Tillage	Frequency	Weed abundance
Strip	Intensity	Weed cover
Ridge		
Primary tillage		
Secondary tillage		

FIGURE 2. SUBCATEGORIES OF THE TOPIC “TILLAGE TYPE”

3. For each identified operation/elements, a comprehensive list of associated technical methods and operations was set, together with their synonymous. These vocabularies served as the essential keywords for the systematic review process. The following example is provided for inversion tillage category (Figure 3):

FIGURE 3: IDENTIFICATION OF KEYWORDS FOR THE INVERSION TILLAGE CATEGORY

4. The keywords were documented on MS-Power Point files, which were then uploaded to a private folder of Oper8 project repository. These files underwent a thorough review process by each contributing partner. During this review, it was determined that the “Tillage type” and “Cultivation depth” tactics, should be merged into a single tactic because distinguishing between them in terms of categorisation proved to be challenging. Once all the contributing partners had reviewed the keywords, they were inserted into search strings following the Scopus guidelines. In particular, these strings were formulated to combine the keywords, representing the components and declinations of each IWM tactic, along with the weed control, representing the performance indicators of the IWM tactics) in relevant TITLE, AUTHOR KEYWORDS and ABSTRACTS information. Limitations that were applied were:

- i) Geographical coverage: Only papers produced by authors affiliated with specific countries were considered. These countries included: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, United Kingdom;
- ii) Time frame: Papers published within the years 2013 to 2022 were included in the search;
- iii) Language: To ensure accessibility to all stakeholders participating in the Oper8 NNs, only papers published in English were selected;
- iv) Publication typology: Research articles were the primary focus of the search, whereas review papers, meta-analyses and opinion papers were excluded.

These stringent criteria were established to narrow the search results and ensure that the selected papers met specific quality and relevance standards for the Oper8 project’s objectives. Hereby, we provide an example of string for the “Tillage type and Cultivation depth”:

TITLE (({tillage} OR {no tillage} OR {no-tillage} OR {conventional tillage} OR {reduced tillage} OR {conservation tillage} OR {conservative tillage} OR {minimum tillage} OR {strip tillage} OR {strip-tillage} OR {ridge tillage} OR {inversion tillage} OR {non-inversion tillage} OR {non inversion tillage} OR {secondary tillage} OR {ploughing} OR {plowing} OR {plow} OR {plough} OR {plows} OR {ploughs} OR {spading} OR {spade} OR {spades} OR {harrowing} OR {harrow} OR {harrows} OR {hoeing} OR {hoe} OR {hoes} OR {cultivation} OR {cultivator} OR {cultivators} OR {disc-o-vator} OR {discovator} OR {disc-o-vators} OR {discovators} OR {grubbing} OR {grubber} OR {grubbers} OR {chiselling} OR {chisel} OR {chisels} OR {subsoiling} OR {subsoiler} OR {subsoilers} OR {stone burier} OR {stone-burier} OR {stone buriers} OR {stone-buriers}) AND ({depth} OR {timing} OR {frequency} OR {intensity} OR {deep} OR {profound} OR {shallow} OR {superficial} OR {surface} OR {double

layer} OR {dual layer} OR {winter} OR {fall} OR {autumn} OR {spring} OR {summer} OR {season} OR {single pass} OR {multiple pass} OR {inter-row} OR {inter rows} OR {between rows} OR {under row} OR {intra row} OR {under-row} OR {intra-row} OR {on the row})) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) **OR ABS** ((({tillage} OR {no tillage} OR {no-tillage} OR {conventional tillage} OR {reduced tillage} OR {conservation tillage} OR {conservative tillage} OR {minimum tillage} OR {strip tillage} OR {strip-tillage} OR {ridge tillage} OR {inversion tillage} OR {non-inversion tillage} OR {non inversion tillage} OR {secondary tillage} OR {ploughing} OR {plowing} OR {plow} OR {plough} OR {plows} OR {ploughs} OR {spading} OR {spade} OR {spades} OR {harrowing} OR {harrow} OR {harrows} OR {hoeing} OR {hoe} OR {hoes} OR {cultivation} OR {cultivator} OR {cultivators} OR {disc-o-vator} OR {discovator} OR {disc-o-vators} OR {discovators} OR {grubbing} OR {grubber} OR {grubbers} OR {chiselling} OR {chisel} OR {chisels} OR {subsoiling} OR {subsoiler} OR {subsoilers} OR {stone burier} OR {stone-burier} OR {stone buriers} OR {stone-buriers})) AND ({depth} OR {timing} OR {frequency} OR {intensity} OR {deep} OR {profound} OR {shallow} OR {superficial} OR {surface} OR {double layer} OR {dual layer} OR {winter} OR {fall} OR {autumn} OR {spring} OR {summer} OR {season} OR {single pass} OR {multiple pass} OR {inter-row} OR {inter rows} OR {between rows} OR {under row} OR {intra row} OR {under-row} OR {intra-row} OR {on the row})) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) **OR AUTHKEY** ((({tillage} OR {no tillage} OR {no-tillage} OR {conventional tillage} OR {reduced tillage} OR {conservation tillage} OR {conservative tillage} OR {minimum tillage} OR {strip tillage} OR {strip-tillage} OR {ridge tillage} OR {inversion tillage} OR {non-inversion tillage} OR {non inversion tillage} OR {secondary tillage} OR {ploughing} OR {plowing} OR {plow} OR {plough} OR {plows} OR {ploughs} OR {spading} OR {spade} OR {spades} OR {harrowing} OR {harrow} OR {harrows} OR {hoeing} OR {hoe} OR {hoes} OR {cultivation} OR {cultivator} OR {cultivators} OR {disc-o-vator} OR {discovator} OR {disc-o-vators} OR {discovators} OR {grubbing} OR {grubber} OR {grubbers} OR {chiselling} OR {chisel} OR {chisels} OR {subsoiling} OR {subsoiler} OR {subsoilers} OR {stone burier} OR {stone-burier} OR {stone buriers} OR {stone-buriers})) AND ({depth} OR {timing} OR {frequency} OR {intensity} OR {deep} OR {profound} OR {shallow} OR {superficial} OR {surface} OR {double layer} OR {dual layer} OR {winter} OR {fall} OR {autumn} OR {spring} OR {summer} OR {season} OR {single pass} OR {multiple pass} OR {inter-row} OR {inter rows} OR {between rows} OR {under row} OR {intra row} OR {under-row} OR {intra-row} OR {on the row})) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) **AND AFFILCOUNTRY** (austria OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2013)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "ar"))

All the other strings used for the search are reported in Appendix 1 to this report.

5. The queries were launched on Scopus on July 15th, 2023, and the results were stored within the Scopus accounts. Subsequently, these results were exported as csv files, imported into a template MS-Excel file (one for each tactic) and shared with contributing partners. At this stage, a total of six thousand, two hundred, and forty-six (**6,246**) potential papers were retrieved, including duplicates selected for several tactics);
6. Considering their respective areas of expertise, specific partners were tasked with leading the initial screening process. This initial screening involved an analysis of the information contained in the title, the author keywords, and the abstract of all the extracted individual papers for a given tactic, in order to check the match between the available information and the screening expectations. Five exclusion criteria were set as illustrated in the Table 5:

Exclusion criteria	Explanation
G	<i>Experiment conducted outside the European territory (EU-27 + United Kingdom)</i>
W	<i>Paper not reporting any of the selected agronomic indicators:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Weed Density (number of weed plants/seeds per unit area);</i> - <i>Weed Soil Cover (% of the unit area covered by weed plants);</i>

Exclusion criteria	Explanation
	- <i>Weed Biomass (dry or fresh weight of above-ground total biomass of weed plants)</i>
S	<i>Systemic Trials (not possible to isolate the effects of the single IWM Tactic from other elements of cropping system; the single Tactic should correspond to a single factor or a single treatment). Factorial trials where different tactics were added in combination to each other, were included, instead</i>
F	<i>The paper did not report on the results of an agricultural field experiment. Greenhouse experiments were retained only if conducted on the soil. Turfgrass or forest tree experiments were not included</i>
O	<i>Other reasons (off-topic)</i>

TABLE 5 – THE FIVE EXCLUSION CRITERIA APPLIED AT THE FIRST STEP OF THE SCREENING

After this initial screening, a total of four thousand, four hundred, and eighty one (4,481) papers were discarded, whereas one thousand, seven hundred, and sixty five (**1,765**) advanced to the next screening step. In both cases, these numbers included duplicates of the same paper, which had been independently selected for different tactics.

7. Whenever available, the PDFs of the full text versions of the selected papers were obtained from the web. These PDFs were then read in full and thoroughly reviewed to verify whether they met the eligibility criteria for inclusion. Ultimately, five hundred and sixty-nine (**569**) papers (seven hundred and sixty-four – 764, including duplicates) were selected for inclusion in the review.
8. From each selected paper, the following information was extracted:
 - IWM tactic: IWM PILLAR and TACTIC CONCERNED, and DESCRIPTION OF THE TESTED TACTIC
 - Study data: Authors, Title, Year of publication, Digital Object Identifier (DOI), Scopus web link (Uniform Resource Locator – URL)
 - Experiment setup: COUNTRY of experiment, CROP TYPE
 - Evaluation: DESCRIPTION OF THE REFERENCE SYSTEM, REFERENCE SYSTEM TYPE (UNTREATED, HERBICIDE-BASED, WEED-FREE, NO-HERBICIDE, NO REFERENCE, DON'T KNOW)
9. The extracted information was transferred into a MS-Excel template to create the final dataset, which is attached to this report (ANNEX 1 or another file?). During the data transfer process, several rules were applied:
 - a. Each paper could be linked to more than one IWM tactic. In such cases, duplicate entries for the same paper were maintained in the database under different IWM tactics;
 - b. In the case that the papers reported on experiments conducted in multiple eligible countries, the entry for that paper was duplicated as many times as the number of additional countries covered by the experiment;

- c. In the case the experiment documented in the papers touched more than one crop typology, the entry of the paper was duplicated as many times as the number of additional crop types covered by the experiment. An exception was made for some papers where no specific reference to one or few crop types was given (e.g., papers where biological control products were tested against weed plants that can be present in several cropping systems). In this case the attribute "MULTIPLE" was used;
- d. In the case the layout of the experiment documented in the papers included multiple reference system, only one entry of the paper was kept, prioritizing, in this order, herbicide-based reference systems, untreated systems and weedy control.

The dataset was subjected to descriptive analysis using the filter and pivot table functions of MS-Excel.

2.2 Methodology for patents search

This part of the state of the art was prepared by applying the same search strings used for the scientific literature review to retrieve patented innovations available on Scopus Patents database. The use of additional search engines (e.g., Google Patents) was avoided because it did not make it possible to make use of the mass of keyword that were thoroughly identified, revised, and selected for each IWM tactic present in the IWM PRAISE framework.

On the same date as literature review, the search strings were launched on Scopus. On the results page, we selected "Patents" instead of "Documents" and then we applied as filters the years (2013 to 2022) and the competent Patent Registration Office that, in our case, was only the European one (European Patent Office – EPO).

The final results were copied and pasted in a MS-Excel template similar to the one used for the scientific literature review. The file was added as a separate worksheet to the MS-Excel folder of the state of the art, annexed to this document as an integrated part of this deliverable.

2.3 Methodology for European and national research projects review

Besides published papers, the scientific knowledge on IWM tactics and tools is made also of the outcomes of research projects conducted on the topic but still not lead to accepted publications on international scientific journals. In Europe, most of research activities are conducted at European level with the support of European Research Framework Programmes (e.g., FP5, FP6, FP7, Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe), including both Research and Innovation Actions (RIA), responding to calls on big societal challenges, or other schemes more oriented to innovation transfer and demonstration activities (e.g., the Life programs). The European Commission regularly collects general information on this kind of projects, as well as their outcomes (e.g., practical abstracts, public reports), on a unique portal called Community Research and Development Information Service – CORDIS (<https://cordis.europa.eu/>).

European funds also, support research conducted at national level. In the agricultural field, a good example is the financial support given to projects funded within the frame of the Rural Development Programs (RDP), thanks to the second pillar fundings of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). Among these projects, the Operational Groups (OGs) are a recently introduced typology to foster collaboration between the academia and the stakeholders of the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS), grouped around a specific challenge (e.g., weed control). Oper8 relies upon eight (8) of this kind of projects, all targeting to test alternative weed control methods to manage weeds without the use of herbicides. OGs outlines and results are collected on the EIP-AGRI website. Although less extensively, this portal also gathers information on other projects funded at national level on agricultural topics through other financial instruments. This list, actually, does not include the whole number of projects funded nationally on the related topics, as this kind of information is only available at national or, much often, at regional level (Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics – NUTS2). Gathering this information is not an easy task as a comprehensive and systematised lists of

all the projects can be not available at each country level. Even harder is to automatically retrieve information on project outputs, such as reports and publications.

In the limited time available for the Task, we decided for convenience to explore only the information on projects available on EU-wide portals, such as CORDIS, LIFE and EIP-AGRI. To easily collect the target information, a digital automatising tool (“crawler”) has been used.

In the World Wide Web's digital ecosystem, most information is tailored for human consumption. Consequently, automated agents face difficulties in extracting data that is both precise and granular. A web crawler is a specialized software application designed to navigate the Internet and archive pertinent data from various sources. The web crawling tool for harvesting project-related data from project programme databases such as CORDIS and LIFE was developed within the SHERPA project. The primary aim of web crawling is the effective collection and central storage of valuable information from many resources. Furthermore, a web crawler must be cognizant of potential constraints imposed by the sources of information. Adopting a "polite" approach—characterized by slow, respectful access to data—is crucial. This aspect underscores the need for the crawler to be resilient as it encounters a diverse array of resources, each with its own set of security measures and data formatting requirements that could potentially derail the entire operation. Additionally, the crawler must be equipped to adhere to a spectrum of communication protocols and application standards that are operational within the Internet's infrastructure. The wideness of the search operation directly correlates with the required robustness of the web crawler.

FIGURE 4. PROCESS FOLLOWED TO EXTRACT DATA ON EUROPEAN AND NATIONAL PROJECTS

Within the framework of the Oper8 project, a specialized web crawler has been deployed to harvest recent and current projects related to specific tactics in weed management. The information about these projects is dispersed across various databases, including but not limited to CORDIS, LIFE, and EIP-AGRI. Currently, the crawler is configured to scan these three databases to identify the most germane projects, extract pertinent data, and archive it within a Google Drive repository. This entire procedure can be autonomously completed within a time span not exceeding 48 hours. The only prerequisite for initiating this automated operation is the provision of a set of keywords germane to the focal area of inquiry. The keywords used in this activity were the same as for the literature review, which reflected the IWM tactics outlined in the IWMPRAISE framework.

The crawler was run between May and August 2023. The outcomes have been exported in MS-Excel files, one for each IWM tactics queried. The outcomes included the following fields (columns):

- Datasource: CORDIS, LIFE or EIP portal
- Acronym: the acronym of the project
- Title: full title of the project
- URL: link to the webpage of the project on the related repository
- Start Date: date (dd/mm/yyyy) or year of the beginning of the project
- Keywords: keywords associated to the project on the repository that were intercepted by the crawler
- Context: general keywords associated to the project (weed or weed control)

The outcomes were screened for eligibility according to the following 3 criteria:

Eligibility criteria	Explanation
G	<i>Project implying experiments conducted outside the European territory (EU-27 + United Kingdom)</i>
F	<i>The project did not deal with agricultural crops. Projects on protected crops grown in greenhouses were retained only if conducted on the soil. Turfgrass or forest tree experiments were not included</i>
O	<i>Other reasons (off-topic)</i>

TABLE 6 – THE ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA APPLIED AT THE OUTCOMES OF THE CRAWLER

To do that, the title of the project and the detailed information retrieved at the URL were examined.

The dataset including only eligible projects has been then expanded to include additional information (coming in new columns), retrieved by visiting case by case the related URL and reading the abstract of the project:

- IWM PILLAR
- IWM TACTIC
- EU/NATIONAL LEVEL: projects were labelled as “EU” if built around an international consortium established within the frame of EU-wide research programmes; if funded at national level, the name of the related country was entered;
- PROJECT CATEGORY: in this column, the framework programme (FP5, FP6, FP7, H2020, LIFE, MARIE-CURIE) or the project type (OG) were specified, respectively for European or national projects. When funded through other schemes, “Research project” was used;

- CROP TYPE: the same categories (ARABLE CROPS, FIELD VEGETABLES, ORCHARDS, OLIVE TREES, VINEYARDS, GRASSLANDS) used for scientific paper review were used. When it was not possible to identify a specific target crop typology, “MULTIPLE” was used. If a specific project related to more than one crop typology, then the row was duplicated as many times as the number of different crop typologies interested by the project, entering in each row the specific crop typology.

The results were then gathered in two distinct datasets, one for European and one for National Projects, building up two distinct worksheets of the dataset in Annex 1.

Part. 3 Description of the outcomes

3.1 Outcomes of the systematic scientific literature review

Out of the seven hundred and sixty-four (764) entries that met the eligibility criteria, approximately thirty eight percent (38%) referred to direct control methods (Figure 5). This is not surprising as direct methods are often perceived as the most effective ones in controlling weeds particularly in the short term. Nevertheless, it is noteworthy to mention that these tactics, in the light of the concept of IWM, should ideally be conceived as a last resort to be employed after all the preventive and cultural methods have been exhausted. Within the category of direct control methods, besides the pre-harvest control (one hundred and one – 101 entries) and the mechanical (sixty-four – 64) and thermal (twenty three – 23) weeding, most of the papers recently published in Europe focused on biological control (seventy-one – 71), an emerging issue that at the moment is limited to research applications. Interestingly, seventeen (17) entries referred to hand weeding, a standard farmer practice especially in field vegetable productions, where it is conceived as an operation complementary to other direct weed control methods.

FIGURE 5. NUMBER OF ENTRIES PER THE IWM TACTICS WITHIN EACH PILLAR OF THE IWM FRAMEWORK

The largest amount of information from the scientific review was related to tillage and cultivation depth tactics (one hundred and thirteen – 113 entries). Together with the other second IWM pillar tactics, they represented twenty-three percent (23%) of the total number of entries. Similar percentage was reached by the fourth pillar (Diverse cropping systems), within which cover crops and intercropping were the most represented tactics. Despite its acknowledged paramount importance in all the integrated crop protection strategies, weed control included, crop rotation was retrieved only in fifteen (15) entries. This is because our eligibility criteria were quite strict and only papers where crop rotation was a factor and not just part of the cropping system, were accepted.

Very limited body of literature was identified for the third pillar (Cultivar choice and crop establishment), linked to sixty-six (66) entries (roughly nine percent – 9%, of the total), and for the fifth one (Monitoring and evaluation), with only fifty-three (53) valid entries. This is peculiar as the fifth pillar is thought to be the core of the IWM framework. Nevertheless, similar results came up also in the EU-H2020 IWM PRAISE project, where the results of participatory trials with farmers conducted in T7.3 clearly showed the tendency of farmers to neglect the importance of an in-deep knowledge of the weed flora present in their field. This actually represents the first step in all the Integrated Pest Management (IPM) strategies, because knowing the target weed or pest species, their abundance, their biological cycles and their ecological roles is crucial and functional to the design of effective IWM and IPM strategies. Additionally, for the fifth pillar it is also worth noting that most of the entries selected in the review were “borderline”, originating from papers where specific Decision Support System (DSS), sensing technology or monitoring instruments were designed,

calibrated and fine-tuned, but not rigorously tested in terms of their impact on weed control, compared to other strategies not utilizing them. This is because of the high level of innovation that characterises these solutions, too new to be widely tested yet against standard practices.

In many cases, the papers reported only on one tactic of the IWM framework (seventy-six percent – 76%, of total cases), but in nineteen percent (19%) of the cases two (2) tactics were deployed. Typically, these involved tactics from same pillar, but some connections between tactics from different pillars were also observed, particularly in relation to sensing technology coupled with mechanical weeding, and to dead mulching, in connection to cover crops. The highest number of converging tactics found in a single paper was four (4), identified in four (4) papers.

In Figure 6, the number of entries per pillar was categorised according to the crop type. Sixty-five percent (65%) of total entries referred to arable crops, which ones represented forty-two percent (42%) of entries related to the first pillar “Direct control”, seventy-six percent (76%) of the second pillar “Field and soil management”, eighty-two percent (82%) of the third pillar “Cultivar choice and crop establishment”, seventy-five percent (75%) of the fourth pillar “Diverse cropping systems” and ninety-six percent (96%) of the fifth pillar “Monitoring and evaluation”. The second most represented crop type was field vegetables (twelve percent – 12%), followed by tree crops (olive trees and orchards) that, all together, represented eleven percent (11%) of the total number of entries. We can notice that vineyards are very few represented in scientific papers on weed management (Figure 6).

FIGURE 6. NUMBER OF ENTRIES PER EACH OF THE FIVE IWM PILLARS, SPLITTED FOR CROP TYPES

As shown in Figure 5, forty-three percent (43%) of the entries came from papers published in the last three (3) years of the decade 2013-2022. We observed a trend of an increasing body of literature produced over time especially on the fourth and the first pillars, where most of the attention was paid to biological control and cover crops as tactics. This trend is clearly consistent with the policy changes occurred in the last five (5) years in the EU, with the proclamation of the EU Green Deal and the Farm to Fork Strategy, and the entry into force of the new CAP (2023-2027). All these policy instruments set the target of considerable pesticide use reduction by 2030 and this might have given strength to research efforts in the field of alternative direct or indirect methods of IWM.

FIGURE 7. NUMBER OF ENTRIES PER YEAR OF PUBLICATION

Considering the geographical coverage of the dataset, the number of entries for each country is shown in Figure 8. The majority of the entries came from experiments conducted in two Mediterranean countries (i.e., Italy and Spain), that represented thirty-six percent (36%) of the total number of entries. Poland was the second most represented country, with a share of fifteen percent (15%) of total entries. For intercropping, the most represented countries were Germany and France, whereas most of the research made on landscape management effect on weed control was apparently done in Hungary. The most widespread topic was tillage type and cultivation depth, present in papers produced in twenty (20) countries, followed by cover crops with sixteen (16) countries represented. The least spread tactics were, instead, water management, seed vigour and sowing depth, with only one (1) country represented (data not shown).

FIGURE 8. NUMBER OF ENTRIES PER COUNTRY

Finally, for what concerns the reference system, as shown in Figure 9, most of the experiments included an untreated control (i.e., a control without chemical or non-chemical weed control). Also, herbicide-free (NO-HERBICIDE) and HERBICIDE-BASED controls were equally important. In two hundred and six (206) cases it was not possible to clearly identify the type of the control and in thirty-four (34) cases there was not actually a reference system, to which the IWM tactic was compared. This information will be important for next Oper8 project steps, when the efficacy of each tested tactic will be assessed, in particular against herbicide-based tactics.

FIGURE 9. NUMBER OF ENTRIES PER TYPE OF REFERENCE SYSTEM

3.2 Outcomes of the patents search

As expected, the search returned very few results. Only thirty (30) patents registered in EU-27 + UK in the last ten (10) years were retrieved. The majority (twenty-five – 25) belonged to the second pillar (Field and Soil management), all in the tactics “Tillage type and Cultivation depth”. Only two (2) patents were retrieved for the first pillar, respectively one for Biological control and one for Pre-harvest control, and three patents were found as related to the fifth pillar, all for Sensing technology as a tactic. The majority of the patents found for the second pillar referred to plough, machinery framework or adjusting/controlling systems. In our opinion, the scarcity of the results reveals three (3) aspects that could be thought as alternative or even complementary explanations:

- in IWM the tendency is in using tools and knowledge formerly available and eventually just to adapt these to the specific aims;
- on the market there is still no cutting-edge technology available for IWM that has been developed in the last ten (10) years;
- there is low interest (or too high costs) in patenting innovative solutions, ranging from product to process innovations, maybe because of the low marginal benefits and the convenience to “copy and paste” innovations that is quite widespread, especially in the agricultural machinery sector.

3.3 Outcomes of the European projects search

A total of seventy-two (72) eligible projects funded at European level are included in the dataset. The total number of entries is one hundred and fifty-seven (157), meaning there are more than two (2) entries per project, on average. This reflects the fact that some projects cover more than one crop typology or more than one IWM tactics. The distribution of entries among IWM tactics and crop typology is shown, respectively, in Figure 10 and Figure 11.

FIGURE 10. NUMBER OF ENTRIES PER IWM TACTICS FOR EUROPEAN PROJECTS

FIGURE 11. NUMBER OF ENTRIES PER EACH OF THE FIVE IWM PILLARS, SPLITTED FOR CROP TYPES, FOR EUROPEAN PROJECTS

Cultivar choice and crop establishment was the IWM pillar for which the highest number of entries were found (sixty-nine – 69, representing the forty-four – 44% of the total). Direct control (thirty-five – 35 entries) and Field and Soil Management (twenty six – 26) were of secondary importance, whereas very few entries were included for Diverse Cropping Systems and Monitoring and Evaluation pillars.

Sowing and transplanting date, Nutrient placement and Biological control were the most represented IWM tactics, representing forty-five percent (45%) of the entries. In many cases, these tactics interested no specific crop typologies, as shown by the highest number of entries found for “Multiple” crops (Figure 12). This likely occurred because many projects focused on the characterisation and study of target weed species (e.g., alien weed species, parasitic weeds) that could be hosted by several crops and that could be controlled by the application of specific tactics of IWM.

FIGURE 12. NUMBER OF ENTRIES PER CROP TYPOLOGY FOR EUROPEAN PROJECTS

Finally, considering the typology of funding programmes, the far highest number of entries came from Horizon 2020 projects, revealing thus a consistent trend with the ones highlighted for scientific papers, namely the increasing number of research activities on IWM topics over time (Figure 13).

FIGURE 13. NUMBER OF ENTRIES PER RESEARCH PROGRAMME FOR EUROPEAN PROJECTS

3.4 Outcomes of the National projects search

A total of fifty-one (51) eligible projects funded at national level are included in the dataset. The total number of entries is one hundred and forty-seven (147), meaning there are almost three (3) entries per project, on average. This reflects the fact that some projects cover more than one crop typology or more than one IWM tactics. The distribution of entries among IWM tactics and crop typology is shown, respectively, in Figure 14 and Figure 15.

FIGURE 14. NUMBER OF ENTRIES PER IWM TACTICS FOR NATIONAL PROJECTS

FIGURE 15. NUMBER OF ENTRIES PER EACH OF THE FIVE IWM PILLARS, SPLITTED FOR CROP TYPES, FOR NATIONAL PROJECTS

As for European projects, also for national ones we got the highest number of entries (sixty one – 61, with forty-one percent – 41% of the total) for the third pillar (Cultivar choice and Crop establishment). At national level, five tactics were not represented at all in the dataset, namely Mowing, Seed Destruction/collection, Liming, Intercropping and DSS. Differently from European projects, Arable crops were the crop category most represented within each pillar. Maybe this is since at European level it is easier to conduct interdisciplinary and basic research, whereas at national level most of the efforts are borne on applied and specific case studies, such as specific crops or weeds.

Overall, arable crops covered fifty-four percent (54%) of the total number of entries (Figure 16). Clearly, because of the rules set for this search, Operational Groups represented most of the research projects funded at National level, covering ninety-four percent (94%) of the total number of the entries (Table 7).

FIGURE 16. NUMBER OF ENTRIES PER CROP TYPOLOGY FOR NATIONAL PROJECTS

RESEARCH PROGRAMME	NUMBER OF ENTRIES
RESEARCH PROJECT	6
OG	137
RDP	4
Total	147

TABLE 7. NUMBER OF ENTRIES PER RESEARCH PROGRAMME FOR NATIONAL PROJECTS

Part. 4 Conclusions

4.1 Summary conclusions on scientific literature review

IWM approach relies on the integration among “many little hammers” that, if applied in a consistent and systemic way, can result in significant results of weed control. However, it is important to note that these outcomes often become apparent only in the medium to long term. These considerations allow us to define some limits of our review of scientific literature.

First, the approach based on systematic review, on one hand, allowed us to disentangle the effect on weeds due to single crop management practices or operations from that of the cropping system as a whole. On the other hand, this led us to a reductionist approach that did not allow to spotlight the importance of a system approach, that is the only win-win solution in IWM. In IWM, it is the synergistic interaction of various components within the farming system that creates an effective weed management strategy. This means that some nuances of the systems approach may not be adequately addressed in this review.

Second, because of the former, our approach unravelled mostly the effect of solutions potentially effective only in the short term, due to the short duration of the studies documented in the literature and intercepted by the search constraints. For instance, mechanical weeding, a tactic often yielding quick results, tends to be well- presented. The relatively short duration of the studies identified in the literature is partly responsible for this emphasis on short- term effectiveness. This may not fully capture the long-term benefits and sustainability of certain IWM practices.

Although, not fully compliant with the PRISMA guidelines, an hybrid approach combining systematic review and scope review at a later stage could be advisable to overcome these limitations. For instance, with such a hybrid approach, it could be feasible to complement the papers that can be retrieved by a systematic review approach with review papers and references cited in both these types of publications, in order to try to fill the knowledge gaps identified in the systematic review.

Nevertheless, this systematic review has contributed to define the burdens of the most advanced knowledge in IWM in EU-27 + UK and also, to test the applicability of the IWM PRAISE framework as a study method to approach scientific literature review.

As part of future activities within the Oper8 project, each National Network Operator (NNO) will have the availability of the papers included in the dataset and this could facilitate the preparation of focus group and NN meetings. Papers related to specific IWM tactics, crop types and countries can be easily retrieved thanks to the Oper8 inventory that will be developed in T2.3 and that will integrate also the metadata extracted from the Scopus search engine (e.g., author keywords and abstracts). Additional efforts can be put in extracting data from the full papers in order to feed the discussion on IWM tactics that is foreseen in WP3. In particular, the selected papers can be exploited to make it available for NNs information on the effectiveness of weed control tactics, as well as on socio-economic and environmental costs and benefits, useful for the completion of T3.2 and T3.3.

Based on these latter data, this literature review will pave the way also for the preparation of scientific reviews and meta-analysis on effectiveness, readiness, and cost-benefit analysis of IWM tactics alternative to herbicide use.

4.2 Summary conclusions on patent search

This part of the state of the art is clearly not sufficient to provide actors involved in the NNs of Oper8 and, in a wider sense, who are part of the AKIS at European level, with new insights on market available solutions. Representatives of the industry involved in focus groups and NNs will be fundamental to complement this limited information with novel technologies that might be available on the market but out of the patents regime.

4.3 Summary conclusions on European and National projects search

The list of research projects conducted at European and national level in the EU on topics related to IWM will make available for the NNOs relevant information to clearly demonstrate for which IWM tactics scientific knowledge has been recently produced and, at the same time to easily spotlight knowledge gaps and identify research priority for the next future. The absence of consolidated up-to-date scientific knowledge, produced with the latest and most advanced approaches, can be considered as a proxy of a higher risk for farmers to put in practice certain tactics. On the other hand, the lack of outcomes of research projects can be also seen as a consequence of the availability of solid knowledge, as in the case of traditional agronomic practices (e.g., crop rotation). Therefore, this information should be duly considered in the detailed evaluation of IWM tactics that will be displaced in WP3 of Oper8.

For the remaining tactics for which the dataset proves the existence of a mass of research activities carried out in the last decade, the information made available with the dataset should be complemented with further details that could be easily retrieved “on-demand” by accessing the CORDIS/LIFE/EIP portals and search for project documents.

Whereas for European project we presume the crawler allowed us to extract the most relevant information, for national projects there might be an even considerable number of experiences funded through other schemes than OG or RDP that is not represented in the dataset. NNOs can try to contact their respective contact points at the responsible institutions and ask for additional information. National and European workshops in WP3 will also allow to share results from these national projects, by involving the participants to take part in the workshops for sharing feedback and experiences.

Part. 5 General Conclusions and Final Remarks

The state of the art produced in Task 2.2 represents a good starting point for technical discussion to be held within the NNs, trying to identify the scientific knowledge and technological solutions supporting specific IWM tactics.

Due to the shortage of time and the extensive efforts put in literature review, it was not possible to extract additional information from the knowledge sources identified, that might have been made easier the life for NNOs when preparing the next activities within national focus groups and networks of stakeholders. For scientific papers, for instance, we were not able to score the effectiveness of the tested solutions against their respective controls. This was not an easy task, indeed, as the weed control performance indicators selected (e.g., weed biomass, weed soil cover, weed density) were not always easy to interpretate. That is why the suggestion for the NNs is to use the dataset first to identify the papers of potential interest for the specific discussion held in their focus groups and then reading the papers to extract the relevant information needed to discuss with the local stakeholders. For national projects, it was not possible to establish strong connections with the Ministries and other National authorities to obtain comprehensive lists of projects funded national about IWM especially for countries under-represented in the list. It is highly advisable for NNs to try to contact the authorities and complement the available information with additional details and sources. For technological solutions, we experienced the highest lack of information on web search engines, such as Scopus. An attempt to improve the dataset may come from exploring other datasets (e.g., Google Patents) or to change the approach, i.e. moving from a systematic review approach to a scope review approach. But we argue that discussion held internally in NNs and focus groups of Oper8 can be resolute, because of the deep knowledge of many stakeholders, above all farmers and representatives of the industry (e.g., seed companies, agrichemical companies, farm machinery companies). We also hypothesise there might be a relevant number of technological solutions that exceed patents that only effective members of the AKIS can help to retrieve.

From the methodological point of view, the use of the IWM PRAISE framework of IWM revealed to be very useful to systematise the information to gather. It was also an excellent education tool as, through its application to literature review and other information source explorations, the users were able to consolidate their knowledge on IWM and to deeply understand the different IWM tactics and strategies. Nevertheless, we must report that the framework was not always easy to adapt to the systematic review approach as in many cases we experienced, on one hand, huge risks of overlapping among different tactics and, on the other hand, weak links of resulting sources of information with the supposedly most closed tactics. Anyway, in general we had a positive impression on the use of the framework, and we consider it as a powerful tool to conduct participatory analyses with NN members at national level. The availability of interactive web tools and factsheets on each single IWM tactics that accompany the framework could only make it easier for Oper8 NNOs to use it, in integration with the dataset, in the in-deep analysis of IWM tactics planned for WP3.

Appendix 1. Search strings used for the scientific literature review.

1. PILLAR DIRECT CONTROL

Biological control

TITLE(((Biological control} OR {Natural enemy} OR {Natural enemies} OR {Biocontrol agents} OR {Biocontrol agent} OR {Bioherbicides} OR {Bioherbicide} OR {Allelopathic plants} OR {Allelopathic plant} OR {Microbial herbicides} OR {Microbial herbicide} OR {Phytophagous insects} OR {Phytophagous insect} OR {Phytophagous nematodes} OR {Parasitic nematode} OR {Plant pathogens} OR {Plant pathogen} OR {Phytophagous mites} OR {Plant extracts} OR {Plant extract} OR {Bacteria} OR {Fungi} OR {Biofumigant crops} OR {Biofumigant crop} OR {Bio-fumigation})) AND ((Weed} OR {Weeds})) OR ABS (((Biological control} OR {Natural enemy} OR {Natural enemies} OR {Biocontrol agents} OR {Biocontrol agent} OR {Bioherbicides} OR {Bioherbicide} OR {Allelopathic plants} OR {Allelopathic plant} OR {Microbial herbicides} OR {Microbial herbicide} OR {Phytophagous insects} OR {Phytophagous insect} OR {Phytophagous nematodes} OR {Parasitic nematode} OR {Plant pathogens} OR {Plant pathogen} OR {Phytophagous mites} OR {Plant extracts} OR {Plant extract} OR {Bacteria} OR {Fungi} OR {Biofumigant crops} OR {Biofumigant crop} OR {Biofumigation})) AND ((Weed} OR {Weeds})) OR AUTHKEY (((Biological control} OR {Natural enemy} OR {Natural enemies} OR {Biocontrol agents} OR {Biocontrol agent} OR {Bioherbicides} OR {Bioherbicide} OR {Allelopathic plants} OR {Allelopathic plant} OR {Microbial herbicides} OR {Microbial herbicide} OR {Phytophagous insects} OR {Phytophagous insect} OR {Phytophagous nematodes} OR {Parasitic nematode} OR {Plant pathogens} OR {Plant pathogen} OR {Phytophagous mites} OR {Plant extracts} OR {Plant extract} OR {Bacteria} OR {Fungi} OR {Biofumigant crops} OR {Biofumigant crop} OR {Biofumigation})) AND ((Weed} OR {Weeds})) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (austria OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR,2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR,2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR,2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR,2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR,2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR,2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR,2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR,2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR,2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR,2013)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE,"English"))

Hand weeding

TITLE (({Hand weeding} OR {Manual weeding} OR {manual weed control} OR {Hand hoe} OR {Hand hoes} OR {Push hoe} OR {Push hoes} OR {Tractor-drawn platform for manual weeding} OR {Tractor-drawn platforms for manual weeding} OR {Self-propelled platform for manual weeding} OR {Self-propelled platforms for manual weeding} OR {Manual weeding tool} OR {Manual weeding tools} OR {hand weeding tool} OR {hand weeding tools} OR {Ergonomic of hand weeding} OR {Ergonomic of manual weeding } OR {Hand weeding cost} OR {Hand weeding costs} OR {Manual weeding cost} OR {Manual weeding costs} OR {Hand weeding labor} OR {Manual weeding labor}) AND ({weed } OR {weeds})) OR ABS (({Hand weeding} OR {Manual weeding} OR {manual weed control} OR {Hand hoe} OR {Hand hoes} OR {Push hoe} OR {Push hoes} OR {Tractor-drawn platform for manual weeding} OR {Tractor-drawn platforms for manual weeding} OR {Self-propelled platform for manual weeding} OR {Self-propelled platforms for manual weeding} OR {Manual weeding tool} OR {Manual weeding tools} OR {hand weeding tool} OR {hand weeding tools} OR {Ergonomic of hand weeding} OR {Ergonomic of manual weeding } OR {Hand weeding cost} OR {Hand weeding costs} OR {Manual weeding cost} OR {Manual weeding costs} OR {Hand weeding labor} OR {Manual weeding labor}) AND ({weed } OR {weeds})) OR AUTHKEY (({Hand weeding} OR {Manual weeding} OR {manual weed control} OR {Hand hoe} OR {Hand hoes} OR {Push hoe} OR {Push hoes} OR {Tractor-drawn platform for manual weeding} OR {Tractor-drawn platforms for manual weeding} OR {Self-propelled platform for manual weeding} OR {Self-propelled platforms for manual weeding} OR {Manual weeding tool} OR {Manual weeding tools} OR {hand weeding tool} OR {hand weeding tools} OR {Ergonomic of hand weeding} OR {Ergonomic of manual weeding } OR {Hand weeding cost} OR {Hand weeding costs} OR {Manual weeding cost} OR {Manual weeding costs} OR {Hand weeding labor} OR {Manual weeding labor}) AND ({weed } OR {weeds})) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (austria OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR

LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2013)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE,"English"))

Mechanical weeding

TITLE (({physical weed control} OR {mechanical weed control} OR {mechanical weed management} OR {inter-row cultivation} OR {intra row cultivation} OR {in row mechanical selective weed control} OR {harrow} OR {harrows} OR {spring tine harrow} OR {spring tine harrows} OR {flex tine harrow} OR {flex tine harrows} OR {universal cultivator} OR {universal cultivators} OR {cultivator} OR {cultivators} OR {inter row cultivator} OR {inter row cultivators} OR {automated inter row cultivator} OR {automated inter row cultivators} OR {hoe} OR {hoes} OR {inter row hoeing} OR {tiller} OR {tillers} OR {inter row rotary tiller} OR {inter row rotary tillers} OR {intra row cultivator} OR {intra row cultivators} OR {automated intra row cultivator} OR {automated intra row cultivators} OR {weeder} OR {weeders} OR {bedder} OR {bedders} OR {row bedder} OR {row bedders} OR {ridging} OR {mulcher} OR {mulchers} OR {mower} OR {mowers} OR {blower} OR {blowers} OR {pneumatic} OR {brushes} OR {brush} OR {torsion weeder} OR {torsion weeders} OR {finger weeder} OR {finger weeders} OR {robotic weeder} OR {robotic weeders} OR {robot} OR {robots}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR ABS (({physical weed control} OR {mechanical weed control} OR {mechanical weed management} OR {inter-row cultivation} OR {intra row cultivation} OR {in row mechanical selective weed control} OR {harrow} OR {harrows} OR {spring tine harrow} OR {spring tine harrows} OR {flex tine harrow} OR {flex tine harrows} OR {universal cultivator} OR {universal cultivators} OR {cultivator} OR {cultivators} OR {inter row cultivator} OR {inter row cultivators} OR {automated inter row cultivator} OR {automated inter row cultivators} OR {hoe} OR {hoes} OR {inter row hoeing} OR {tiller} OR {tillers} OR {inter row rotary tiller} OR {inter row rotary tillers} OR {intra row cultivator} OR {intra row cultivators} OR {automated intra row cultivator} OR {automated intra row cultivators} OR {weeder} OR {weeders} OR {bedder} OR {bedders} OR {row bedder} OR {row bedders} OR {ridging} OR {mulcher} OR {mulchers} OR {mower} OR {mowers} OR {blower} OR {blowers} OR {pneumatic} OR {brushes} OR {brush} OR {torsion weeder} OR {torsion weeders} OR {finger weeder} OR {finger weeders} OR {robotic weeder} OR {robotic weeders} OR {robot} OR {robots}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR AUTHKEY (({physical weed control} OR {mechanical weed control} OR {mechanical weed management} OR {inter-row cultivation} OR {intra row cultivation} OR {in row mechanical selective weed control} OR {harrow} OR {harrows} OR {spring tine harrow} OR {spring tine harrows} OR {flex tine harrow} OR {flex tine harrows} OR {universal cultivator} OR {universal cultivators} OR {cultivator} OR {cultivators} OR {inter row cultivator} OR {inter row cultivators} OR {automated inter row cultivator} OR {automated inter row cultivators} OR {hoe} OR {hoes} OR {inter row hoeing} OR {tiller} OR {tillers} OR {inter row rotary tiller} OR {inter row rotary tillers} OR {intra row cultivator} OR {intra row cultivators} OR {automated intra row cultivator} OR {automated intra row cultivators} OR {weeder} OR {weeders} OR {bedder} OR {bedders} OR {row bedder} OR {row bedders} OR {ridging} OR {mulcher} OR {mulchers} OR {mower} OR {mowers} OR {blower} OR {blowers} OR {pneumatic} OR {brushes} OR {brush} OR {torsion weeder} OR {torsion weeders} OR {finger weeder} OR {finger weeders} OR {robotic weeder} OR {robotic weeders} OR {robot} OR {robots}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (austria OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2013)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")))

Mowing

TITLE (({Mowing} OR {Rotary mowing} OR {Flail mowing} OR {Sickle mowing} OR {Gang mowing} OR {Brush mowing} OR {Riding lawn mowers} OR {Riding lawn mower} OR {Walk-behind mowers} OR {Walk-behind mower} OR {Flail mowers} OR {Flail mower} OR {Self-propelled flail mowers} OR {Pull-behind sickle bar mowers} OR {Pull-behind sickle bar mower} OR {Hand-held sickle bar mowers} OR {Hand-held sickle bar mower} OR {Triplex mowers} OR {Triplex mower} OR {Quad mowers} OR {Quad mower} OR {Skid steer mounted brush mowers} OR {Skid steer mounted brush mower} OR {Brush cutters} OR {Brush cutter}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR ABS (({Mowing} OR {Rotary mowing} OR {Flail mowing} OR {Sickle mowing} OR {Gang mowing} OR {Brush mowing} OR {Riding lawn mowers} OR {Riding lawn mower} OR {Walk-behind mowers} OR {Walk-behind mower} OR {Flail mowers} OR {Flail mower} OR {Self-propelled flail mowers} OR {Pull-behind sickle bar mowers} OR {Pull-behind sickle bar mower} OR {Hand-held sickle bar mowers} OR {Hand-held sickle bar mower} OR {Triplex mowers} OR {Triplex mower} OR {Quad mowers} OR {Quad mower} OR {Skid steer mounted brush mowers} OR {Skid steer mounted brush mower} OR {Brush cutters} OR {Brush cutter}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR AUTHKEY (({Mowing} OR {Rotary mowing} OR {Flail mowing} OR {Sickle

mowing} OR {Gang mowing} OR {Brush mowing} OR {Riding lawn mowers} OR {Riding lawn mower} OR {Walk-behind mowers} OR {Walk-behind mower} OR {Flail mowers} OR {Flail mower} OR {Self-propelled flail mowers} OR {Pull-behind sickle bar mowers} OR {Pull-behind sickle bar mower} OR {Hand-held sickle bar mowers} OR {Hand-held sickle bar mower} OR {Triplex mowers} OR {Triplex mower} OR {Quad mowers} OR {Quad mower} OR {Skid steer mounted brush mowers} OR {Skid steer mounted brush mower} OR {Brush cutters} OR {Brush cutter}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (austria OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2013)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar"))

Pre-harvest control

TITLE (({Pre-harvest herbicides} OR {Pre-harvest herbicide} OR {Chemical herbicides} OR {Chemical herbicide} OR {Selective herbicides} OR {Selective herbicide} OR {Non-selective herbicides} OR {Non-selective herbicides} OR {Non selective herbicides} OR {Non selective herbicides} OR {Broad-spectrum herbicides} OR {Broad-spectrum herbicide} OR {Broad spectrum herbicides} OR {Broad spectrum herbicide} OR {Systemic herbicides} OR { Systemic herbicide} OR {Contact herbicides} OR {Contact herbicide} OR {2,4-D} OR {MCPA} OR {Glyphosate} OR {Paraquat} OR {Saflufenacil} OR {Carfentrazone-ethyl} OR {Diquat}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR ABS (({Pre-harvest herbicides} OR {Pre-harvest herbicide} OR {Chemical herbicides} OR {Chemical herbicide} OR {Selective herbicides} OR {Selective herbicide} OR {Non-selective herbicides} OR {Non-selective herbicides} OR {Non selective herbicides} OR {Non selective herbicides} OR {Broad-spectrum herbicides} OR {Broad-spectrum herbicide} OR {Broad spectrum herbicides} OR {Broad spectrum herbicide} OR {Systemic herbicides} OR { Systemic herbicide} OR {Contact herbicides} OR {Contact herbicide} OR {2,4-D} OR {MCPA} OR {Glyphosate} OR {Paraquat} OR {Saflufenacil} OR {Carfentrazone-ethyl} OR {Diquat}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR AUTHKEY (({Pre-harvest herbicides} OR {Pre-harvest herbicide} OR {Chemical herbicides} OR {Chemical herbicide} OR {Selective herbicides} OR {Selective herbicide} OR {Non-selective herbicides} OR {Non-selective herbicides} OR {Non selective herbicides} OR {Non selective herbicides} OR {Broad-spectrum herbicides} OR {Broad-spectrum herbicide} OR {Broad spectrum herbicides} OR {Broad spectrum herbicide} OR {Systemic herbicides} OR { Systemic herbicide} OR {Contact herbicides} OR {Contact herbicide} OR {2,4-D} OR {MCPA} OR {Glyphosate} OR {Paraquat} OR {Saflufenacil} OR {Carfentrazone-ethyl} OR {Diquat}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (austria OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2013)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar"))

Thermal weeding

TITLE (({physical weed control} OR {thermal weed control} OR {physical weed management} OR {thermal weed management} OR {flaming} OR {infrared} OR {infra-red} OR {steaming} OR {laser} OR {microwave} OR {micro-wave} OR {uv} OR {ultra violet} OR {hot foam} OR {hot-foam} OR {electric} OR {hot air} OR {hot-air} OR {Eweeder} OR {electrophysical} OR {electro-physical} OR {electrical} OR {hot water}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR ABS (({physical weed control} OR {thermal weed control} OR {physical weed management} OR {thermal weed management} OR {flaming} OR {infrared} OR {infra-red} OR {steaming} OR {laser} OR {microwave} OR {micro-wave} OR {uv} OR {ultra violet} OR {hot foam} OR {hot-foam} OR {electric} OR {hot air} OR {hot-air} OR {Eweeder} OR {electrophysical} OR {electro-physical} OR {electrical} OR {hot water}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR AUTHKEY (({physical weed control} OR {thermal weed control} OR {physical weed management} OR {thermal weed management} OR {flaming} OR {infrared} OR {infra-red} OR {steaming} OR {laser} OR {microwave} OR {micro-wave} OR {uv} OR {ultra violet} OR {hot foam} OR {hot-foam} OR {electric} OR {hot air} OR {hot-air} OR {Eweeder} OR {electrophysical} OR {electro-physical} OR {electrical} OR {hot water}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (austria OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2013)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English"))

Weed/seed collection/destruction

TITLE (({weed seed collection} OR {weed seed destruction} OR {harvest weed seed control} OR {HWSC} OR {weed seed retention} OR {chaff narrow-windrow weed seed} OR {chaff carts weed seed } OR {chaff lining weed seed} OR { chaff tramlining weed seed} OR {bale direct system weed seed} OR {combine harvester weed seed collection} OR { Integrated Harrington Seed Destructor } OR {iHSD} OR { Seed Terminator } OR { Redekop seed control unit } OR { weed hog } OR { weed seed mill } OR { chaff processing impact mill } OR { weed seed grind } OR { weed seed devitalization} OR { weed seed thermal devitalization} OR {Narrow-windrow burning weed seed})) OR ABS (({weed seed collection} OR {weed seed destruction} OR {harvest weed seed control} OR {HWSC} OR {weed seed retention} OR {chaff narrow-windrow weed seed} OR {chaff carts weed seed } OR {chaff lining weed seed} OR { chaff tramlining weed seed} OR {bale direct system weed seed} OR {combine harvester weed seed collection} OR { Integrated Harrington Seed Destructor } OR {iHSD} OR { Seed Terminator } OR { Redekop seed control unit } OR { weed hog } OR { weed seed mill } OR { chaff processing impact mill } OR { weed seed grind } OR { weed seed devitalization} OR { weed seed thermal devitalization} OR {Narrow-windrow burning weed seed})) OR AUTHKEY (({weed seed collection} OR {weed seed destruction} OR {harvest weed seed control} OR {HWSC} OR {weed seed retention} OR {chaff narrow-windrow weed seed} OR {chaff carts weed seed } OR {chaff lining weed seed} OR { chaff tramlining weed seed} OR {bale direct system weed seed} OR {combine harvester weed seed collection} OR { Integrated Harrington Seed Destructor } OR {iHSD} OR { Seed Terminator } OR { Redekop seed control unit } OR { weed hog } OR { weed seed mill } OR { chaff processing impact mill } OR { weed seed grind } OR { weed seed devitalization} OR { weed seed thermal devitalization} OR {Narrow-windrow burning weed seed})) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (austria OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2013)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English"))

2. PILLAR FIELD AND SOIL MANAGEMENT

Dead Mulching

TITLE ((({mulch}) AND ({dead} OR {sheeted} OR {sheeting} OR {particle} OR {polypropylene} OR {polythene} OR {plastic} OR {biodegradable} OR {bioplastic} OR {geotextile} OR {paper} OR {newspaper} OR {carpet} OR {bark} OR {wood} OR {rock} OR {gravel} OR {shell} OR {straw} OR {hay} OR {grass clipping} OR {crop waste} OR {industrial waste} OR {cover crop} OR {crop residue} OR {crop wastes} OR {industrial wastes} OR {cover crops} OR {crop residues}) AND ({management} OR {spatial management} OR {temporal management} OR {under-row} OR {under-row} OR {inter-row} OR {inter rows} OR {full surface} OR {broadcast} OR {localised} OR {band} OR {strip} OR {duration} OR {long term} OR {long-term} OR {short term} OR {short-term} OR {permanent} OR {temporary} OR {seasonal} OR {annual} OR {spring} OR {summer} OR {autumn} OR {fall} OR {winter} OR {renewal})) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR ABS ((({mulch}) AND ({dead} OR {sheeted} OR {sheeting} OR {particle} OR {polypropylene} OR {polythene} OR {plastic} OR {biodegradable} OR {bioplastic} OR {geotextile} OR {paper} OR {newspaper} OR {carpet} OR {bark} OR {wood} OR {rock} OR {gravel} OR {shell} OR {straw} OR {hay} OR {grass clipping} OR {crop waste} OR {industrial waste} OR {cover crop} OR {crop residue} OR {crop wastes} OR {industrial wastes} OR {cover crops} OR {crop residues}) AND ({management} OR {spatial management} OR {temporal management} OR {under-row} OR {under-row} OR {inter-row} OR {inter rows} OR {full surface} OR {broadcast} OR {localised} OR {band} OR {strip} OR {duration} OR {long term} OR {long-term} OR {short term} OR {short-term} OR {permanent} OR {temporary} OR {seasonal} OR {annual} OR {spring} OR {summer} OR {autumn} OR {fall} OR {winter} OR {renewal})) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR AUTHKEY ((({mulch}) AND ({dead} OR {sheeted} OR {sheeting} OR {particle} OR {polypropylene} OR {polythene} OR {plastic} OR {biodegradable} OR {bioplastic} OR {geotextile} OR {paper} OR {newspaper} OR {carpet} OR {bark} OR {wood} OR {rock} OR {gravel} OR {shell} OR {straw} OR {hay} OR {grass clipping} OR {crop waste} OR {industrial waste} OR {cover crop} OR {crop residue} OR {crop wastes} OR {industrial wastes} OR {cover crops} OR {crop residues}) AND ({management} OR {spatial management} OR {temporal management} OR {under-row} OR {under-row} OR {inter-row} OR {inter rows} OR {full surface} OR {broadcast} OR {localised} OR {band} OR {strip} OR {duration} OR {long term} OR {long-term} OR {short term} OR {short-term} OR {permanent} OR {temporary} OR {seasonal} OR {annual} OR {spring} OR {summer} OR {autumn} OR {fall} OR {winter} OR {renewal})) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (austria OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR ,

2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2013)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar"))

Liming

TITLE (({liming} OR {lime} OR {limestone} OR {soil salinity} OR {soil pH} OR {soil acidity} OR {acid soil} OR {acid soils} OR {calcium} OR {magnesium}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR ABS (({liming} OR {lime} OR {limestone} OR {soil salinity} OR {soil pH} OR {soil acidity} OR {acid soil} OR {acid soils} OR {calcium} OR {magnesium}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR AUTHKEY (({liming} OR {lime} OR {limestone} OR {soil salinity} OR {soil pH} OR {soil acidity} OR {acid soil} OR {acid soils} OR {calcium} OR {magnesium}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (austria OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2013)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar"))

Nutrient placement

TITLE ((({amendment} OR {fertiliser} OR {nutrient} {amendments} OR {fertilisers} OR {nutrients} OR {slurry} OR {digestate} OR {manure} OR {compost} OR {biochar} OR {hydrochar} OR {slurries} OR {digestates} OR {manures} OR {composts} OR {biochars} OR {hydrochars}) AND ({placement} OR {application} OR {broadcast} OR {localised} OR {band} OR {in furrow} OR {in-furrow} OR {surface} OR {incorporation} OR {foliar} OR {fertigation} OR {sprinkler irrigation} OR {drip irrigation} OR {sub-irrigation} OR {subsurface} OR {sub-surface} OR {sub irrigation} OR {top dressing} OR {top-dressing} OR {pre-tillage} OR {plowing} OR {injection} OR {harrowing} OR {grubbing} OR {plow} OR {plough} OR {harrow} OR {grubber} OR {plows} OR {ploughs} OR {harrows} OR {grubbers} OR {pre-sowing} OR {cultivation} OR {cultivator} OR {cultivators} OR {hoeing} OR {hoe} OR {hoes}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds}))) OR ABS ((({amendment} OR {fertiliser} OR {nutrient} {amendments} OR {fertilisers} OR {nutrients} OR {slurry} OR {digestate} OR {manure} OR {compost} OR {biochar} OR {hydrochar} OR {slurries} OR {digestates} OR {manures} OR {composts} OR {biochars} OR {hydrochars}) AND ({placement} OR {application} OR {broadcast} OR {localised} OR {band} OR {in furrow} OR {in-furrow} OR {surface} OR {incorporation} OR {foliar} OR {fertigation} OR {sprinkler irrigation} OR {drip irrigation} OR {sub-irrigation} OR {subsurface} OR {sub-surface} OR {sub irrigation} OR {top dressing} OR {top-dressing} OR {pre-tillage} OR {plowing} OR {injection} OR {harrowing} OR {grubbing} OR {plow} OR {plough} OR {harrow} OR {grubber} OR {plows} OR {ploughs} OR {harrows} OR {grubbers} OR {pre-sowing} OR {cultivation} OR {cultivator} OR {cultivators} OR {hoeing} OR {hoe} OR {hoes}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds}))) OR AUTHKEY ((({amendment} OR {fertiliser} OR {nutrient} {amendments} OR {fertilisers} OR {nutrients} OR {slurry} OR {digestate} OR {manure} OR {compost} OR {biochar} OR {hydrochar} OR {slurries} OR {digestates} OR {manures} OR {composts} OR {biochars} OR {hydrochars}) AND ({placement} OR {application} OR {broadcast} OR {localised} OR {band} OR {in furrow} OR {in-furrow} OR {surface} OR {incorporation} OR {foliar} OR {fertigation} OR {sprinkler irrigation} OR {drip irrigation} OR {sub-irrigation} OR {subsurface} OR {sub-surface} OR {sub irrigation} OR {top dressing} OR {top-dressing} OR {pre-tillage} OR {plowing} OR {injection} OR {harrowing} OR {grubbing} OR {plow} OR {plough} OR {harrow} OR {grubber} OR {plows} OR {ploughs} OR {harrows} OR {grubbers} OR {pre-sowing} OR {cultivation} OR {cultivator} OR {cultivators} OR {hoeing} OR {hoe} OR {hoes}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds}))) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (austria OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2013)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar"))

Seedbed preparation

TITLE (({seedbed} OR {seedbed preparation} OR {ridge} OR {ridging} OR {raised bed} OR {flat bed} OR {sunken bed} OR {raised beds} OR {flat beds} OR {sunken beds} OR {false seedbed} OR {stale seedbed} OR {solarization} OR {stone burier} OR {stone buriers} OR {flaming} OR {secondary tillage}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR ABS (({seedbed} OR {seedbed preparation} OR {ridge} OR {ridging} OR {raised bed} OR {flat bed} OR {sunken bed} OR {raised beds} OR {flat beds} OR {sunken beds} OR {false seedbed} OR {stale seedbed} OR {solarization} OR {stone burier} OR {stone buriers} OR {flaming} OR {secondary tillage}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR AUTHKEY (({seedbed} OR {seedbed preparation} OR {ridge} OR {ridging} OR {raised bed} OR {flat bed} OR {sunken bed} OR {raised beds} OR {flat beds} OR {sunken beds} OR {false seedbed} OR {stale seedbed} OR {solarization} OR {stone burier} OR {stone buriers} OR {flaming} OR {secondary tillage}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (austria

OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2013)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar"))

Stubble management

TITLE (({stubble} OR {stubbles}) AND ({management} OR {Fallow} OR {Burning} OR {ploughing} OR {plowing} OR {plough} OR {plow} OR {ploughs} OR {plows} OR {stubble retention} OR {retention} OR {Cultivation} OR {Cultivator} OR {Cultivators} OR {harrowing} OR {harrow} OR {harrows} OR {incorporation} OR {Shredding} OR {Shredder} OR {Shredders} OR {Cleaning} OR {Cleaner} OR {Cleaners} OR {Grubbing} OR {Grubber} OR {Grubbers}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds}))) OR ABS ((({stubble} OR {stubbles}) AND ({management} OR {Fallow} OR {Burning} OR {ploughing} OR {plowing} OR {plough} OR {plow} OR {ploughs} OR {plows} OR {stubble retention} OR {retention} OR {Cultivation} OR {Cultivator} OR {Cultivators} OR {harrowing} OR {harrow} OR {harrows} OR {incorporation} OR {Shredding} OR {Shredder} OR {Shredders} OR {Cleaning} OR {Cleaner} OR {Cleaners} OR {Grubbing} OR {Grubber} OR {Grubbers}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds}))) OR AUTHKEY ((({stubble} OR {stubbles}) AND ({management} OR {Fallow} OR {Burning} OR {ploughing} OR {plowing} OR {plough} OR {plow} OR {ploughs} OR {plows} OR {stubble retention} OR {retention} OR {Cultivation} OR {Cultivator} OR {Cultivators} OR {harrowing} OR {harrow} OR {harrows} OR {incorporation} OR {Shredding} OR {Shredder} OR {Shredders} OR {Cleaning} OR {Cleaner} OR {Cleaners} OR {Grubbing} OR {Grubber} OR {Grubbers}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds}))) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (austria OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2013)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar"))

Tillage type and cultivation depth

TITLE ((({tillage} OR {no tillage} OR {no-tillage} OR {conventional tillage} OR {reduced tillage} OR {conservation tillage} OR {conservative tillage} OR {minimum tillage} OR {strip tillage} OR {strip-tillage} OR {ridge tillage} OR {inversion tillage} OR {non-inversion tillage} OR {non inversion tillage} OR {secondary tillage} OR {ploughing} OR {plowing} OR {plow} OR {plough} OR {plows} OR {ploughs} OR {spading} OR {spade} OR {spades} OR {harrowing} OR {harrow} OR {harrows} OR {hoeing} OR {hoe} OR {hoes} OR {cultivation} OR {cultivator} OR {cultivators} OR {disc-o-vator} OR {discovator} OR {disc-o-vators} OR {discovators} OR {grubbing} OR {grubber} OR {grubbers} OR {chiselling} OR {chisel} OR {chisels} OR {subsoiling} OR {subsoiler} OR {subsoilers} OR {stone burier} OR {stone-burier} OR {stone buriers} OR {stone-buriers}) AND ({depth} OR {timing} OR {frequency} OR {intensity} OR {deep} OR {profound} OR {shallow} OR {superficial} OR {surface} OR {double layer} OR {dual layer} OR {winter} OR {fall} OR {autumn} OR {spring} OR {summer} OR {season} OR {single pass} OR {multiple pass} OR {inter-row} OR {inter rows} OR {between rows} OR {under row} OR {intra row} OR {under-row} OR {intra-row} OR {on the row})) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR ABS ((({tillage} OR {no tillage} OR {no-tillage} OR {conventional tillage} OR {reduced tillage} OR {conservation tillage} OR {conservative tillage} OR {minimum tillage} OR {strip tillage} OR {strip-tillage} OR {ridge tillage} OR {inversion tillage} OR {non-inversion tillage} OR {non inversion tillage} OR {secondary tillage} OR {ploughing} OR {plowing} OR {plow} OR {plough} OR {plows} OR {ploughs} OR {spading} OR {spade} OR {spades} OR {harrowing} OR {harrow} OR {harrows} OR {hoeing} OR {hoe} OR {hoes} OR {cultivation} OR {cultivator} OR {cultivators} OR {disc-o-vator} OR {discovator} OR {disc-o-vators} OR {discovators} OR {grubbing} OR {grubber} OR {grubbers} OR {chiselling} OR {chisel} OR {chisels} OR {subsoiling} OR {subsoiler} OR {subsoilers} OR {stone burier} OR {stone-burier} OR {stone buriers} OR {stone-buriers}) AND ({depth} OR {timing} OR {frequency} OR {intensity} OR {deep} OR {profound} OR {shallow} OR {superficial} OR {surface} OR {double layer} OR {dual layer} OR {winter} OR {fall} OR {autumn} OR {spring} OR {summer} OR {season} OR {single pass} OR {multiple pass} OR {inter-row} OR {inter rows} OR {between rows} OR {under row} OR {intra row} OR {under-row} OR {intra-row} OR {on the row})) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR AUTHKEY ((({tillage} OR {no tillage} OR {no-tillage} OR {conventional tillage} OR {reduced tillage} OR {conservation tillage} OR {conservative tillage} OR {minimum tillage} OR {strip tillage} OR {strip-tillage} OR {ridge tillage} OR {inversion tillage} OR {non-inversion tillage} OR {non inversion tillage} OR {secondary tillage} OR {ploughing} OR {plowing} OR {plow} OR {plough} OR {plows} OR {ploughs} OR {spading} OR {spade} OR {spades} OR {harrowing} OR {harrow} OR {harrows} OR {hoeing} OR {hoe} OR {hoes} OR {cultivation} OR {cultivator} OR {cultivators} OR {disc-o-vator} OR {discovator} OR {disc-o-vators} OR {discovators} OR {grubbing} OR {grubber} OR {grubbers} OR {chiselling} OR {chisel} OR {chisels} OR {subsoiling} OR {subsoiler} OR {subsoilers} OR {stone burier} OR {stone-burier} OR {stone buriers} OR {stone-buriers}) AND ({depth} OR {timing} OR {frequency} OR {intensity} OR {deep} OR {profound} OR {shallow} OR {superficial} OR {surface} OR {double layer} OR {dual layer} OR {winter} OR {fall} OR {autumn} OR {spring} OR

{summer} OR {season} OR {single pass} OR {multiple pass} OR {inter-row} OR {inter rows} OR {between rows} OR {under row} OR {intra row} OR {under-row} OR {intra-row} OR {on the row})) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (austria OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2013))) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar"))

Water management

TITLE (({water management} OR {drainage} OR {irrigation} OR {watering}) AND ({drip} OR {trickle} OR {micro} OR {micro-irrigation} OR {low volume} OR {localised} OR {sprinkle} OR {above ground} OR {above-ground} OR {under-ground} OR {underground} OR {over head} OR {overhead} OR {aerial} OR {surface} OR {air} OR {subterranean} OR {underground} OR {subsurface} OR {sub-surface} OR {subirrigation} OR {flooding} OR {on the row} OR {under row} OR {intra-row} OR {under trellis} OR {between rows} OR {between the rows} OR {inter-row} OR {inter row} OR {frequency} OR {alternate} OR {occasional} OR {deficit} OR {duration} OR {quantity} OR {location} OR {period} OR {season}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR ABS (({water management} OR {drainage} OR {irrigation} OR {watering}) AND ({drip} OR {trickle} OR {micro} OR {micro-irrigation} OR {low volume} OR {localised} OR {sprinkle} OR {above ground} OR {above-ground} OR {under-ground} OR {underground} OR {over head} OR {overhead} OR {aerial} OR {surface} OR {air} OR {subterranean} OR {underground} OR {subsurface} OR {sub-surface} OR {subirrigation} OR {flooding} OR {on the row} OR {under row} OR {intra-row} OR {under trellis} OR {between rows} OR {between the rows} OR {inter-row} OR {inter row} OR {frequency} OR {alternate} OR {occasional} OR {deficit} OR {duration} OR {quantity} OR {location} OR {period} OR {season}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR AUTHKEY (({water management} OR {drainage} OR {irrigation} OR {watering}) AND ({drip} OR {trickle} OR {micro} OR {micro-irrigation} OR {low volume} OR {localised} OR {sprinkle} OR {above ground} OR {above-ground} OR {under-ground} OR {underground} OR {over head} OR {overhead} OR {aerial} OR {surface} OR {air} OR {subterranean} OR {underground} OR {subsurface} OR {sub-surface} OR {subirrigation} OR {flooding} OR {on the row} OR {under row} OR {intra-row} OR {under trellis} OR {between rows} OR {between the rows} OR {inter-row} OR {inter row} OR {frequency} OR {alternate} OR {occasional} OR {deficit} OR {duration} OR {quantity} OR {location} OR {period} OR {season}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (austria OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2013))) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar"))

3. PILLAR CULTIVAR CHOICE AND CROP ESTABLISHMENT

Cultivar choice

TITLE (({Cultivar choice} OR {Cultivar} OR {Cultivars} OR {Crop genotype} OR {Crop genotypes} OR {Crop variety} OR {Crop varieties} OR {Crop populations} OR {Crop population} OR {Composite cross populations} OR {Composite cross population} OR {Evolutionary populations} OR {Evolutionary population} OR {Heterogeneous plant material} OR {Cultivar mixtures} OR {Cultivar mixture} OR {Variety mixtures} OR {Variety mixture} OR {Cultivar mixes} OR {Cultivar mix} OR {Variety mixes} OR {Variety mix} OR {Competitive genotypes} OR {Competitive genotype} OR {Crop competition} OR {Crop competitiveness} OR {Growth rates} OR {Growth rate} OR {Growing rate} OR {Competitive ability} OR {Crop genetic diversity}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR ABS (({Cultivar choice} OR {Cultivar} OR {Cultivars} OR {Crop genotype} OR {Crop genotypes} OR {Crop variety} OR {Crop varieties} OR {Crop populations} OR {Crop population} OR {Composite cross populations} OR {Composite cross population} OR {Evolutionary populations} OR {Evolutionary population} OR {Heterogeneous plant material} OR {Cultivar mixtures} OR {Cultivar mixture} OR {Variety mixtures} OR {Variety mixture} OR {Cultivar mixes} OR {Cultivar mix} OR {Variety mixes} OR {Variety mix} OR {Competitive genotypes} OR {Competitive genotype} OR {Crop competition} OR {Crop competitiveness} OR {Growth rates} OR {Growth rate} OR {Growing rate} OR {Competitive ability} OR {Crop genetic diversity}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR AUTHKEY (({Cultivar choice} OR {Cultivar} OR {Cultivars} OR {Crop genotype} OR {Crop genotypes} OR {Crop variety} OR {Crop varieties} OR {Crop populations} OR {Crop population} OR {Composite cross populations} OR {Composite cross population} OR {Evolutionary populations} OR {Evolutionary population} OR {Heterogeneous plant material} OR {Cultivar mixtures} OR {Cultivar mixture} OR {Variety mixtures} OR {Variety mixture} OR {Cultivar mixes} OR {Cultivar mix} OR

{Variety mixes} OR {Variety mix} OR {Competitive genotypes} OR {Competitive genotype} OR {Crop competition} OR {Crop competitiveness} OR {Growth rates} OR {Growth rate} OR {Growing rate} OR {Competitive ability} OR {Crop genetic diversity}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (austria OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2013)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar"))

Seed rate

TITLE (({Seed Rate} OR {Seed Rates} OR {Increased seeding rates} OR {Increased seeding rate} OR {Reduced seeding rates} OR {Reduced seeding rate} OR {Decreased seeding rates} OR {Decreased seeding rate} OR {Crop density} OR {Crop densities} OR {Crop populations} OR {Crop population} OR {Intra-row} OR {Seed cost} OR {Seed costs}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR ABS (({Seed Rate} OR {Seed Rates} OR {Increased seeding rates} OR {Increased seeding rate} OR {Reduced seeding rates} OR {Reduced seeding rate} OR {Decreased seeding rates} OR {Decreased seeding rate} OR {Crop density} OR {Crop densities} OR {Crop populations} OR {Crop population} OR {Intra-row} OR {Seed cost} OR {Seed costs}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR AUTHKEY (({Seed Rate} OR {Seed Rates} OR {Increased seeding rates} OR {Increased seeding rate} OR {Reduced seeding rates} OR {Reduced seeding rate} OR {Decreased seeding rates} OR {Decreased seeding rate} OR {Crop density} OR {Crop densities} OR {Crop populations} OR {Crop population} OR {Intra-row} OR {Seed cost} OR {Seed costs}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (austria OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2013)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar"))

Seed vigour

TITLE ((({seed} OR {seeds} OR {seed vigor} OR {seed vigour}) AND ({emergence} OR {emergence rate} OR {germination} OR {germinability} OR {germination rate} OR {coating} OR {biocoating} OR {bio-coating} OR {activation} OR {activated} OR {priming} OR {bioactivation} OR {bio-activation} OR {bio-activated} OR {dormancy} OR {dormant} OR {potassium nitrate} OR {gibberellin} OR {gibberellic acid})) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR ABS ((({seed} OR {seeds} OR {seed vigor} OR {seed vigour}) AND ({emergence} OR {emergence rate} OR {germination} OR {germinability} OR {germination rate} OR {coating} OR {biocoating} OR {bio-coating} OR {activation} OR {activated} OR {priming} OR {bioactivation} OR {bio-activation} OR {bio-activated} OR {dormancy} OR {dormant} OR {potassium nitrate} OR {gibberellin} OR {gibberellic acid})) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR AUTHKEY ((({seed} OR {seeds} OR {seed vigor} OR {seed vigour}) AND ({emergence} OR {emergence rate} OR {germination} OR {germinability} OR {germination rate} OR {coating} OR {biocoating} OR {bio-coating} OR {activation} OR {activated} OR {priming} OR {bioactivation} OR {bio-activation} OR {bio-activated} OR {dormancy} OR {dormant} OR {potassium nitrate} OR {gibberellin} OR {gibberellic acid})) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (austria OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2013)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar"))

Seeding pattern

TITLE (({Seeding pattern} OR {Seeding patterns} OR {Narrow row spacing} OR {Canopy closure} OR {Crop spatial arrangement} OR {Crop row orientation} OR {Crop spatial arrangements} OR {Crop row orientations} OR {Interspecific competition} OR {Broadcast sowing} OR {Band sowing} OR {Wide row spacing} OR {Crop spacing} OR {Row spacing}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR ABS (({Seeding pattern} OR {Seeding patterns} OR {Narrow row spacing} OR {Canopy closure} OR {Crop spatial arrangement} OR {Crop row orientation} OR {Crop spatial arrangements} OR {Crop row orientations} OR {Interspecific competition} OR {Broadcast sowing} OR {Band sowing} OR {Wide row spacing} OR {Crop spacing} OR {Row spacing}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR AUTHKEY (({Seeding pattern} OR {Seeding patterns} OR {Narrow row spacing} OR {Canopy closure} OR {Crop spatial arrangement} OR {Crop row orientation} OR {Crop spatial arrangements} OR {Crop row orientations} OR

{Interspecific competition} OR {Broadcast sowing} OR {Band sowing} OR {Wide row spacing} OR {Crop spacing} OR {Row spacing} AND ({weed} OR {weeds}) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (austria OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2013)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar"))

Sowing depth

TITLE (({sowing} OR {seeding} OR {drilling} OR {crop establishment}) AND ({depth} OR {shallow} OR {superficial} OR {deep} OR {profound} OR {uniform}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR ABS (({sowing} OR {seeding} OR {drilling} OR {crop establishment}) AND ({depth} OR {shallow} OR {superficial} OR {deep} OR {profound} OR {uniform}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR AUTHKEY (({sowing} OR {seeding} OR {drilling} OR {crop establishment}) AND ({depth} OR {shallow} OR {superficial} OR {deep} OR {profound} OR {uniform}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (austria OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2013)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar"))

Sowing/Transplanting date

TITLE (({sowing} OR {seeding} OR {transplanting} OR {crop establishment}) AND ({seasonality} OR {spring} OR {season} OR {summer} OR {fall} OR {autumn} OR {winter} OR {early} OR {earliness} OR {lateness} OR {late} OR {delayed})) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR ABS (({sowing} OR {seeding} OR {transplanting} OR {crop establishment}) AND ({seasonality} OR {spring} OR {season} OR {summer} OR {fall} OR {autumn} OR {winter} OR {early} OR {earliness} OR {lateness} OR {late} OR {delayed})) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR AUTHKEY (({sowing} OR {seeding} OR {transplanting} OR {crop establishment}) AND ({seasonality} OR {spring} OR {season} OR {summer} OR {fall} OR {autumn} OR {winter} OR {early} OR {earliness} OR {lateness} OR {late} OR {delayed})) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (austria OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2013)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar"))

Transplanting

TITLE (({crop establishment} OR {transplanting} OR {planting} OR {transplant} OR {transplanted crop} OR {transplanted crops}) AND ({manual} OR {mechanical} OR {automatic} OR {semi-automatic} OR {hand} OR {by-hand} OR {coultter planter} OR {punch planter} OR {coultter planters} OR {punch planters}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR ABS (({crop establishment} OR {transplanting} OR {planting} OR {transplant} OR {transplanted crop} OR {transplanted crops}) AND ({manual} OR {mechanical} OR {automatic} OR {semi-automatic} OR {hand} OR {by-hand} OR {coultter planter} OR {punch planter} OR {coultter planters} OR {punch planters}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR AUTHKEY (({crop establishment} OR {transplanting} OR {planting} OR {transplant} OR {transplanted crop} OR {transplanted crops}) AND ({manual} OR {mechanical} OR {automatic} OR {semi-automatic} OR {hand} OR {by-hand} OR {coultter planter} OR {punch planter} OR {coultter planters} OR {punch planters}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (austria OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2013)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar"))

4. PILLAR DIVERSE CROPPING SYSTEMS

Cover crops

TITLE (({cover crop} OR {cover crops} OR {cover cropping} OR {green manure} OR {green manures} OR {green manuring} OR {subsidiary crop} OR {subsidiary crops} OR {agroecological service crop} OR {agroecological service crops} OR {living mulch} OR {dead mulch}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR ABS (({cover crop} OR {cover crops} OR {cover cropping} OR {green manure} OR {green manures} OR {green manuring} OR {subsidiary crop} OR {subsidiary crops} OR {agroecological service crop} OR {agroecological service crops} OR {living mulch} OR {dead mulch}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR AUTHKEY (({cover crop} OR {cover crops} OR {cover cropping} OR {green manure} OR {green manures} OR {green manuring} OR {subsidiary crop} OR {subsidiary crops} OR {agroecological service crop} OR {agroecological service crops} OR {living mulch} OR {dead mulch}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (austria OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2013)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar"))

Crop rotation

TITLE (({crop rotation} OR {crop rotations} OR {crop sequence} OR {crop sequences} OR {second harvest} OR {fallow} OR {bare soil} OR {forage crops} OR {forage crop} OR {grass-clover} OR {grass clover} OR {meadows} OR {intermediate crops} OR {intermediate crop} OR {rotational forage} OR {rotational forages}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR ABS (({crop rotation} OR {crop rotations} OR {crop sequence} OR {crop sequences} OR {second harvest} OR {fallow} OR {bare soil} OR {forage crops} OR {forage crop} OR {grass-clover} OR {grass clover} OR {meadows} OR {intermediate crops} OR {intermediate crop} OR {rotational forage} OR {rotational forages}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR AUTHKEY (({crop rotation} OR {crop rotations} OR {crop sequence} OR {crop sequences} OR {second harvest} OR {fallow} OR {bare soil} OR {forage crops} OR {forage crop} OR {grass-clover} OR {grass clover} OR {meadows} OR {intermediate crops} OR {intermediate crop} OR {rotational forage} OR {rotational forages}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (austria OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2013)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar"))

Field margin management

TITLE (({field margins} OR {field margin} OR {fences} OR {fence} OR {tree row} OR {tree rows} OR {hedgerows} OR {hedgerow} OR {walls} OR {wall} OR {terraces} OR {terrace} OR {ditches} OR {ditch} OR {drainage} OR {drainages} OR {grass strips} OR {grass strip} OR {flower strips} OR {flower strip} OR {buffer strips} OR {buffer strip} OR {crop strips} OR {crop strip} OR {alley cropping} OR {alley crops} OR {seminatural habitats} OR {semi-natural habitats} OR {seminatural habitat} OR {semi-natural habitat}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR ABS (({field margins} OR {field margin} OR {fences} OR {fence} OR {tree row} OR {tree rows} OR {hedgerows} OR {hedgerow} OR {walls} OR {wall} OR {terraces} OR {terrace} OR {ditches} OR {ditch} OR {drainage} OR {drainages} OR {grass strips} OR {grass strip} OR {flower strips} OR {flower strip} OR {buffer strips} OR {buffer strip} OR {crop strips} OR {crop strip} OR {alley cropping} OR {alley crops} OR {seminatural habitats} OR {semi-natural habitats} OR {seminatural habitat} OR {semi-natural habitat}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR AUTHKEY (({field margins} OR {field margin} OR {fences} OR {fence} OR {tree row} OR {tree rows} OR {hedgerows} OR {hedgerow} OR {walls} OR {wall} OR {terraces} OR {terrace} OR {ditches} OR {ditch} OR {drainage} OR {drainages} OR {grass strips} OR {grass strip} OR {flower strips} OR {flower strip} OR {buffer strips} OR {buffer strip} OR {crop strips} OR {crop strip} OR {alley cropping} OR {alley crops} OR {seminatural habitats} OR {semi-natural habitats} OR {seminatural habitat} OR {semi-natural habitat}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (austria OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (

PUBYEAR, 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2013)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "ar"))

Intercropping

TITLE (({intercrop} OR {intercropping} OR {polyculture} OR {polycultures} OR {variety mixtures} OR {variety mixture} OR {variety mix} OR {variety mixes} OR {crop association} OR {crop associations}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR ABS (({intercrop} OR {intercropping} OR {polyculture} OR {polycultures} OR {variety mixtures} OR {variety mixture} OR {variety mix} OR {variety mixes} OR {crop association} OR {crop associations}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR AUTHKEY (({intercrop} OR {intercropping} OR {polyculture} OR {polycultures} OR {variety mixtures} OR {variety mixture} OR {variety mix} OR {variety mixes} OR {crop association} OR {crop associations}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (austria OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2013)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "ar"))

Landscape management

TITLE (({agriculture landscape} OR {rural landscape} OR {rural landscapes} OR {agricultural landscapes} OR {agrolandscapes} OR {landscape complexity} OR {landscape connectedness} OR {wood forestry} OR {grasslands} OR {meadows} OR {mixed farming} OR {agroforestry} OR {livestock} OR {crop prevalence} OR {grazing} OR {pastures} OR {silvo-pastoral} OR {agro-silvo-pastoral} OR {agrosilvopastoral} OR {silvopastoral} OR {silvo-arable} OR {silvoarable} OR {permaculture} OR {synergic agriculture} OR {syntropic agriculture} OR {seminatural habitats} OR {semi-natural habitats} OR {semi-natural areas} OR {seminatural areas} OR {ecological focus areas} OR {ecological focus area} OR {hedgerow} OR {windbreak} OR {riparial strips} OR {shrubs} OR {flower strips} OR {fallow} OR {woodland} OR {alleyways} OR {crop pattern} OR {crop spatial arrangement} OR {crop design} OR {mosaic crops} OR {scattered crops} OR {monoculture} OR {ecological corridors} OR {ecological connections} OR {ecological infrastructures} OR {crop pattern} OR {spatial arrangement} OR {neighbour fields} OR {neighbour field}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR ABS (({agriculture landscape} OR {rural landscape} OR {rural landscapes} OR {agricultural landscapes} OR {agrolandscapes} OR {landscape complexity} OR {landscape connectedness} OR {wood forestry} OR {grasslands} OR {meadows} OR {mixed farming} OR {agroforestry} OR {livestock} OR {crop prevalence} OR {grazing} OR {pastures} OR {silvo-pastoral} OR {agro-silvo-pastoral} OR {agrosilvopastoral} OR {silvopastoral} OR {silvo-arable} OR {silvoarable} OR {permaculture} OR {synergic agriculture} OR {syntropic agriculture} OR {seminatural habitats} OR {semi-natural habitats} OR {semi-natural areas} OR {seminatural areas} OR {ecological focus areas} OR {ecological focus area} OR {hedgerow} OR {windbreak} OR {riparial strips} OR {shrubs} OR {flower strips} OR {fallow} OR {woodland} OR {alleyways} OR {crop pattern} OR {crop spatial arrangement} OR {crop design} OR {mosaic crops} OR {scattered crops} OR {monoculture} OR {ecological corridors} OR {ecological connections} OR {ecological infrastructures} OR {crop pattern} OR {spatial arrangement} OR {neighbour fields} OR {neighbour field}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR AUTHKEY (({agriculture landscape} OR {rural landscape} OR {rural landscapes} OR {agricultural landscapes} OR {agrolandscapes} OR {landscape complexity} OR {landscape connectedness} OR {wood forestry} OR {grasslands} OR {meadows} OR {mixed farming} OR {agroforestry} OR {livestock} OR {crop prevalence} OR {grazing} OR {pastures} OR {silvo-pastoral} OR {agro-silvo-pastoral} OR {agrosilvopastoral} OR {silvopastoral} OR {silvo-arable} OR {silvoarable} OR {permaculture} OR {synergic agriculture} OR {syntropic agriculture} OR {seminatural habitats} OR {semi-natural habitats} OR {semi-natural areas} OR {seminatural areas} OR {ecological focus areas} OR {ecological focus area} OR {hedgerow} OR {windbreak} OR {riparial strips} OR {shrubs} OR {flower strips} OR {fallow} OR {woodland} OR {alleyways} OR {crop pattern} OR {crop spatial arrangement} OR {crop design} OR {mosaic crops} OR {scattered crops} OR {monoculture} OR {ecological corridors} OR {ecological connections} OR {ecological infrastructures} OR {crop pattern} OR {spatial arrangement} OR {neighbour fields} OR {neighbour field}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (austria OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2013)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "ar"))

5. PILLAR MONITORING AND EVALUATION

DSS

TITLE (({DSS} OR {decision support systems} OR {decision support system} OR {decision support tool} OR {decision support tools} OR {mobile app} OR {mobile apps} OR {economic threshold} OR {economic thresholds} OR {crop model} OR {crop models} OR {automated system} OR {automated systems} OR {advisory system} OR {advisory systems} OR {information system} OR {information systems}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR ABS (({DSS} OR {decision support systems} OR {decision support system} OR {decision support tool} OR {decision support tools} OR {mobile app} OR {mobile apps} OR {economic threshold} OR {economic thresholds} OR {crop model} OR {crop models} OR {automated system} OR {automated systems} OR {advisory system} OR {advisory systems} OR {information system} OR {information systems}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR AUTHKEY (({DSS} OR {decision support systems} OR {decision support system} OR {decision support tool} OR {decision support tools} OR {mobile app} OR {mobile apps} OR {economic threshold} OR {economic thresholds} OR {crop model} OR {crop models} OR {automated system} OR {automated systems} OR {advisory system} OR {advisory systems} OR {information system} OR {information systems}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (44weden44 OR 44weden44 OR 44weden44a OR 44weden44 OR cyprus OR 44weden44 OR 44weden44 OR 44weden44 OR finland OR 44weden OR 44weden44 OR 44weden OR hungary OR 44weden44 OR 44wede OR 44weden OR 44weden44a44 OR 44weden44a44d OR malta OR 44weden44a44ds OR 44weden OR 44weden44a OR 44weden44 OR 44weden44a OR 44weden44a OR spain OR 44weden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2013))) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")))

Scouting

TITLE (({weed scouting} OR {weed identification} OR {weed survey} OR {field survey} OR {field surveys} OR {weed monitoring} OR {visual assessment} OR {visual assessments} OR {weed detection} OR {competitive species} OR {weed population} OR {weed populations} OR {weed communities} OR {weed community} OR {seedbank} OR {weed counting} OR {weed mapping}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR ABS (({weed scouting} OR {weed identification} OR {weed survey} OR {field survey} OR {field surveys} OR {weed monitoring} OR {visual assessment} OR {visual assessments} OR {weed detection} OR {competitive species} OR {weed population} OR {weed populations} OR {weed communities} OR {weed community} OR {seedbank} OR {weed counting} OR {weed mapping}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR AUTHKEY (({weed scouting} OR {weed identification} OR {weed survey} OR {field survey} OR {field surveys} OR {weed monitoring} OR {visual assessment} OR {visual assessments} OR {weed detection} OR {competitive species} OR {weed population} OR {weed populations} OR {weed communities} OR {weed community} OR {seedbank} OR {weed counting} OR {weed mapping}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (austria OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2013))) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar")))

SENSING TECHNOLOGIES

TITLE (({sensors} OR {sensor} OR {sensing technology} OR {sensing technologies} OR {remote sensing} OR {satellite} OR {proximal sensors} OR {proximal sensor} OR {drones} OR {drone} OR {UAV} OR {UAVs} OR {unmanned aerial vehicle} OR {unmanned aerial vehicles} OR {UGV} OR {UGVs} OR {unmanned ground vehicle} OR {unmanned ground vehicles} OR {unmanned on-ground vehicle} OR {unmanned on-ground vehicles} OR {RGB camera} OR {RGB cameras} OR {visible cameras} OR {visible camera} OR {imagery} OR {image analysis} OR {artificial intelligence} OR {AI} OR {hyperspectral cameras} OR {hyperspectral camera} OR {hyperspectral imagery} OR {multispectral cameras} OR {multispectral cameras} OR {multispectral imagery} OR {NDVI} OR {multispectral imagery} OR {image-reflectance sensors} OR { image-reflectance sensor} OR {depth cameras} OR {depth camera} OR {optical distance sensors} OR {optical distance sensor} OR {computer vision} OR {deep learning} OR {computer learning} OR {machine learning} OR {convolutional neural networks} OR {neural networks} OR {convolutional

neural network} OR {neural network} OR {multi-sensors} OR {multi-sensor}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR ABS (({sensors} OR {sensor} OR {sensing technology} OR {sensing technologies} OR {remote sensing} OR {satellite} OR {proximal sensors} OR {proximal sensor} OR {drones} OR {drone} OR {UAV} OR {UAVs} OR {unmanned aerial vehicle} OR {unmanned aerial vehicles} OR {UGV} OR {UGVs} OR {unmanned ground vehicle} OR {unmanned ground vehicles} OR {unmanned on-ground vehicle} OR {unmanned on-ground vehicles} OR {RGB camera} OR {RGB cameras} OR {visible cameras} OR {visible camera} OR {imagery} OR {image analysis} OR {artificial intelligence} OR {AI} OR {hyperspectral cameras} OR {hyperspectral camera} OR {hyperspectral imagery} OR {multispectral cameras} OR {multispectral cameras} OR {multispectral imagery} OR {NDVI} OR {multispectral imagery} OR {image-reflectance sensors} OR { image-reflectance sensor} OR {depth cameras} OR {depth camera} OR {optical distance sensors} OR {optical distance sensor} OR {computer vision} OR {deep learning} OR {computer learning} OR {machine learning} OR {convolutional neural networks} OR {neural networks} OR {convolutional neural network} OR {neural network} OR {multi-sensors} OR {multi-sensor}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) OR AUTHKEY (({sensors} OR {sensor} OR {sensing technology} OR {sensing technologies} OR {remote sensing} OR {satellite} OR {proximal sensors} OR {proximal sensor} OR {drones} OR {drone} OR {UAV} OR {UAVs} OR {unmanned aerial vehicle} OR {unmanned aerial vehicles} OR {UGV} OR {UGVs} OR {unmanned ground vehicle} OR {unmanned ground vehicles} OR {unmanned on-ground vehicle} OR {unmanned on-ground vehicles} OR {RGB camera} OR {RGB cameras} OR {visible cameras} OR {visible camera} OR {imagery} OR {image analysis} OR {artificial intelligence} OR {AI} OR {hyperspectral cameras} OR {hyperspectral camera} OR {hyperspectral imagery} OR {multispectral cameras} OR {multispectral cameras} OR {multispectral imagery} OR {NDVI} OR {multispectral imagery} OR {image-reflectance sensors} OR { image-reflectance sensor} OR {depth cameras} OR {depth camera} OR {optical distance sensors} OR {optical distance sensor} OR {computer vision} OR {deep learning} OR {computer learning} OR {machine learning} OR {convolutional neural networks} OR {neural networks} OR {convolutional neural network} OR {neural network} OR {multi-sensors} OR {multi-sensor}) AND ({weed} OR {weeds})) AND AFFILCOUNTRY (austria OR belgium OR bulgaria OR croatia OR cyprus OR czechia OR denmark OR estonia OR finland OR france OR germany OR greece OR hungary OR ireland OR italy OR latvia OR lithuania OR luxembourg OR malta OR netherlands OR poland OR portugal OR romania OR slovakia OR slovenia OR spain OR sweden OR {united kingdom}) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2013)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar"))

